

On Independence and SCC-Recursiveness in Assumption-Based Argumentation

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Abstract

We introduce a notion of conditional independence in (flat) assumption-based argumentation (ABA), where independence between (sets of) assumptions amounts to the presence of information about one set of assumptions not impacting the acceptability of another. We study general properties, computational complexity, and the relation to independence in abstract argumentation. In light of the high computational complexity of deciding independence, we introduce sound methods for checking independence in polynomial time via two different routes: the first utilizes the strongly connected components (SCCs) of the instantiated abstract argumentation framework; the second exploits the structure of the ABA framework directly. Along the way, we introduce the notion of SCC-recursiveness for ABA.

1 Introduction

The ability to recognize and manage (in)dependence is crucial in symbolic reasoning at large [Darwiche and Pearl, 1994; Darwiche, 1997; Lang *et al.*, 2002; Rienstra *et al.*, 2020]. It plays an essential role in causal reasoning [Pearl, 2009], e.g., in probabilistic models, where (in)dependence between variables is built into graphical representations such as Bayesian networks [Geiger *et al.*, 1990]. The ability to determine independence contributes to the explainability [Halpern and Pearl, 2001] and trustworthiness [Belle *et al.*, 2024] of reasoning systems, while also improving efficiency by empowering breaking problems down so that they can be managed more effectively.

In this paper, we study conditional independence in computational argumentation, which captures how different parts of the argumentative information can be logically separated. Two prominent areas therein are abstract argumentation, coined by the seminal paper of Dung (1995), and structured argumentation, as overviewed by Besnard *et al.* (2014b). Unlike abstract argumentation, where arguments are considered abstract, structured argumentation frameworks focus on the structure of the arguments, enabling a finer-grained analysis of the arguments and relations. *Assumption-based argumentation (ABA)* [Bondarenko *et al.*, 1997; Ćyras *et al.*, 2018] is a

well-known form of structured argumentation, whose building blocks are assumptions (defeasible elements) and inference rules. We illustrate this with the following example.

Example 1.1. *Alice, Bob, and Carol plan a tandem trip; we consider assumptions a (Alice cycles), b (Bob cycles), and c (Carol cycles) for each of our protagonists. Naturally, only two of them cycle at the same time, that is, not all our assumptions can be true at once. We capture the relations between our assumptions with inference rules; e.g., “if Bob and Carol cycle then Alice does not” is captured by the rule ($\bar{a} \leftarrow b, c$), here, \bar{a} is the contrary of a . Crucially, if the weather is bad (d) nobody can cycle. On the bright side, then there is no need to water the plants (w) outside. Also, Alice thinks about bringing her book (k), but if she cycles, it might be too heavy.¹*

ABA has been broadly studied computationally [Toni, 2013; Ćyras *et al.*, 2021a; Craven and Toni, 2016; Lehtonen *et al.*, 2024a; Lehtonen *et al.*, 2024b]. ABA is also widely applicable, e.g., in healthcare [Ćyras *et al.*, 2021b], to provide explanations [Ćyras *et al.*, 2021a], for causal discovery [Russo *et al.*, 2024], and planning [Fan, 2018]. In all these settings, a good understanding of independence between various components in ABA frameworks (ABAFs) is crucial. However, to date the study of independence within ABA remains underexplored. Actually, with the notable exception of the conditional independence analysis in abstract argumentation [Rienstra *et al.*, 2020], the topic has been largely neglected in the computational argumentation literature so far.

Turning our attention to ABA, we address the following question: *under what conditions are two (sets of) assumptions independent from each other, relative to a (potentially empty) set of assumptions that is considered prior knowledge?* In other words, does the choice of truth values for one set of assumptions restrict the available choices for the truth values of another set, given the truth values for a third set are fixed?

Example 1.2 (Example 1.1 cont.). *Let us find out if Alice and Bob influence each other’s cycling activities. First, are a and b (unconditionally) independent of each other? The answer to that question is positive: knowing that Alice cycles does not give us any information about Bob, Alice could cycle with either Bob or Carol; similarly, if Alice does not cycle we do not know whether Bob cycles; either Bob and Carol*

¹A formalization is given in Example 3.2.

cycle together or the weather could have ruined their trip. In contrast, a and b depend on each other, given c : knowing that Carol cycles implies that one of the other two cycles as well.

Note that w and k depend on each other, because there is no way to reject both of them at the same time. They are independent when given information about $\{a\}$, $\{d\}$, or $\{b, c\}$.

Identifying conditional independence in ABA is computationally challenging, as we will show. To alleviate the high computational complexity we exploit the structure of ABA and explore *SCC-recursiveness* for ABAFs. Rienstra et al. (2020) demonstrate the advantages of SCC-recursiveness for efficiently checking conditional independence between arguments, based on the SCCs of an abstract argumentation framework (AF) [Dung, 1995]. Despite these considerable computational advantages, SCC-recursiveness has not received attention in the context of structured argumentation so far. In the scope of our independence studies for ABA, we tackle this issue and propose an SCC-recursive schema for ABA semantics alongside sound independence checks for assumptions in ABAFs.

Overall, we make the following contributions, for a well-studied fragment of ABA whereby assumptions cannot be inferred (known as *flat* ABA) and where assumptions, their contraries and any sentences in inference rules are atomic.

- We introduce conditional independence in ABA and study its properties. We analyze its computational complexity and reveal the close relation of independence in ABAFs and AFs. We also settle the complexity of the corresponding decision problems for AFs. Section 4
- We introduce sound and poly-time methods for checking independence in ABA via two different routes:
 - (1) applying the approach by Rienstra et al. (2020) to a suitable AF instantiation for ABAFs; Section 5.1
 - (2) exploiting the structure of the ABAF directly, based on the SCCs of the so-called dependency graph [Rapberger et al., 2022]. Section 5.3
- To facilitate route (2), we introduce SCC-recursiveness for ABA and show that all semantics under consideration satisfy this property. Section 5.2

Due to space restrictions, we focus on complete-based semantics; analogous results for admissible semantics, alongside with proofs and further discussions can be found in the appendices.

2 Related Work

To address the challenges of computationally demanding dependency models, researchers [Verma and Pearl, 1988; Rienstra et al., 2020] have proposed sound (but potentially incomplete) Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) representations to check independence. In the context of computational argumentation, Rienstra et al. (2020) identify a way to transform AFs into DAGs, based on their SCCs, to express (some) dependencies between arguments. Our study of the relation between SCCs in ABA and independence is inspired by this work. However, differently from their work, we focus on structured argumentation in the form of ABA.

Heyninck (2023) proposes a generic framework for studying independence in approximation fixpoint theory, applicable to any logic with fixpoint semantics, including logic programs under partial stable models and well-founded model semantics. Since the latter are instances of ABA in general, and of the restricted form of ABA we consider, the resulting framework in [Heyninck, 2023] is applicable to our setting, too. That being said, our focus lies on the relation to abstract argumentation, and the relation between independence and SCCs (which we newly introduce in this paper for ABA).

Some works use reasoning with independence information to perform causal discovery with ABA [Russo et al., 2024] or paradigms related to ABA, such as ASP [Zhalama et al., 2019]. This line of work is orthogonal to ours, as we focus on studying independence in ABA, rather than using ABA for ascertaining independence for causal discovery. Another work [Besnard et al., 2014a] defines an approach to reasoning about causes via argumentation, which, like in our case, is structured but built on classical logic and including ontologies. It does not consider independence in argumentation.

3 Background

A directed graph is a pair $G = (V, E)$ where V is a set of vertices and $E \subseteq V^2$. A (un)directed path p is a sequence $v_1 \dots v_n$, $v_i \in V$, $v_i \neq v_j$, $i \neq j$, with $(v_i, v_{i+1}) \in E$ (or $(v_{i+1}, v_i) \in E$); a cycle is a sequence $v_n v_1 \dots v_n$ where $v_1 \dots v_n$ is a directed path. G is a directed acyclic graph (DAG) if it contains no directed cycles. For a vertex set $U \subseteq V$, $PA_G(U) = \{w \in V \mid (w, u) \in E, u \in U\} \setminus U$ are the parents of U , $AN_G(U) = \{w \in V \mid \exists u \in U, p = (w, \dots, u) \text{ directed path}\} \setminus U$ the ancestors of U . We say $v \in V$ is a descendant of U , if $U \cap AN_G(\{v\}) \neq \emptyset$. We denote by $DD_G(v)$ the set of all descendants and by $ND_G(v)$ the set of all non-descendants and non-parents of U .

3.1 Assumption-based Argumentation

We recall assumption-based argumentation (ABA) [Čyryš et al., 2018]. We assume a deductive system $(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R})$, where \mathcal{L} is a formal language, i.e., a set of sentences, and \mathcal{R} is a set of inference rules over \mathcal{L} . A rule $r \in \mathcal{R}$ has the form $a_0 \leftarrow a_1, \dots, a_n$ with $a_i \in \mathcal{L}$. We write $head(r) = a_0$ and $body(r) = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ for the possibly empty body of r .

Definition 3.1. An ABA framework (ABAF) is a tuple $(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ with a deductive system $(\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R})$, a non-empty set $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ of assumptions, and contrary function $\neg : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{L}$.

Unless otherwise specified, we assume a unique contrary a_c for each assumption $a \in \mathcal{A}$. We write \bar{a} to denote a_c .

Example 3.2. We formalise the introductory Example 1.1 as ABAF D with assumptions $\{a, b, c, d, w, k\}$, their contraries, and inference rules, $(\bar{v} \leftarrow d)$, $(\bar{d} \leftarrow v)$ for $v \in \{a, b, c\}$, and

$$\bar{a} \leftarrow b, c \quad \bar{b} \leftarrow a, c \quad \bar{c} \leftarrow a, c \quad \bar{k} \leftarrow a \quad \bar{w} \leftarrow d$$

Below, we fix an arbitrary ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$. A sentence $p \in \mathcal{L}$ is *tree-derivable* from assumptions $A \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and rules $R \subseteq \mathcal{R}$, denoted by $A \vdash_R p$ (tree-derivation), if there is a finite rooted labelled tree T such that the root is labelled with p , the set of labels for the leaves of T is equal to

A or $A \cup \{\top\}$, and there is a surjective mapping from the set of internal nodes to R , satisfying that for each internal node v , there is $r \in R$, s.t. v is labelled with $head(r)$, and the set of all successor nodes corresponds to $body(r)$ or \top if $body(r) = \emptyset$. We say p is derivable (in D) iff there is a tree-derivation $A \vdash_R p$, $A \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, $R \subseteq \mathcal{R}$. We call $A \vdash p$ an (ABA) argument if there is $R \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ s.t. $A \vdash_R p$. Arguments of the form $\{a\} \vdash a$, $a \in \mathcal{A}$ are assumption arguments, arguments with $R \neq \emptyset$ rule-based arguments. Each assumption argument is unique; we identify assumption arguments with their assumptions.

By $Th_D(A) = \{p \mid \exists A \vdash p\}$ we denote the set of all claims derivable from assumptions A in D . We let $\bar{A} = \{\bar{a} \mid a \in A\}$. The set A attacks $B \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ if there is $A' \subseteq A$, $b \in B$ s.t. $A' \vdash \bar{b}$. A is conflict-free if it does not attack itself; A is admissible if it is conflict-free and defends itself.

A semantics σ is a function assigning ABAF a set of σ -labellings. We recall complete, grounded, preferred, and stable semantics (abbr. *co*, *gr*, *pr*, *st*) [Schulz and Toni, 2017].

Definition 3.3. A labelling is a (partial) function $\lambda : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow L$, $L = \{in, out, und\}$. For $A \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we let $\lambda_A : A \rightarrow L$ denote a partial labelling of A ; $\lambda|_A$ denotes the restriction of λ to A . For $lab \in L$, $lab(\lambda) = \{x \in \mathcal{A} \mid \lambda(x) = lab\}$.

Definition 3.4. $\lambda : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow L$ is a complete labelling (abbr. *co-labelling*) of an ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \neg)$ iff for each $a \in \mathcal{A}$,

- $\lambda(a) = in$ iff for all $B \vdash \bar{a}$, there is $b \in B$ s.t. $\lambda(b) = out$;
- $\lambda(a) = out$ iff there is $B \vdash \bar{a}$ s.t. $\lambda(b) = in$ for all $b \in B$.

A co-labelling λ is grounded iff $und(\lambda)$ is \subseteq -maximal among all co-labellings of F ; preferred iff $in(\lambda)$ is \subseteq -maximal among all co-labellings of F ; and stable iff $und(\lambda) = \emptyset$.

For semantics σ , the set Λ_σ denotes the set of all σ -labellings of ABAF D . For $A \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we say λ_A is σ -compatible with D if there is $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$ s.t. $\lambda|_A = \lambda_A$.

Assumption 3.5. We focus on ABAFs which are flat, i. e., for each rule $r \in \mathcal{R}$, $head(r) \notin \mathcal{A}$ (no assumption can be derived, and finite, i. e., $\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}$ are finite; moreover, each sentence in $s \in \mathcal{L}$ is atomic and derivable, i. e., there is $A \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ s.t. $A \vdash s$, and each rule is stated explicitly (given as input).

ABAFs and Abstract Argumentation An argumentation framework (AF) [Dung, 1995] is a directed graph $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$ where $\mathbb{A} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ are arguments and $\mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbb{A}^2$ are attacks. We fix a non-finite set \mathcal{U} of arguments. For $x, y \in \mathbb{A}$, if $(x, y) \in R$ we say x attacks y ; $E \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ defends x if it attacks each attacker of x ; E is conflict-free if it does not attack itself; and admissible if it is conflict-free and defends all $x \in E$.

We recall labelling-based complete, grounded, preferred, and stable semantics (abbr. *co*, *gr*, *pr*, *st*) for AFs, following [Caminada and Pigozzi, 2011]. Analogous to ABAFs, a labelling is a function $\lambda : \mathbb{A} \rightarrow L$ (cf. Definition 3.3).

Definition 3.6. A labelling $\lambda : \mathbb{A} \rightarrow L$ is a complete labelling (abbr. *co-labelling*) of an AF $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$ iff for each $x \in \mathbb{A}$,

- $\lambda(x) = in$ iff $\lambda(y) = out$ for every attacker y of x ;
- $\lambda(x) = out$ iff $\lambda(y) = in$ for some attacker y of x .

A co-labelling λ is grounded iff $und(\lambda)$ is \subseteq -maximal among all co-labellings of F ; preferred iff $in(\lambda)$ is \subseteq -maximal among all co-labellings of F ; and stable iff $und(\lambda) = \emptyset$.

We use Λ_σ , analogous to ABAFs (cf. below Definition 3.4).

ABAFs are closely related to AFs [Čypras *et al.*, 2018].

Definition 3.7. The associated AF $F_D = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$ of an ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ is given by $\mathbb{A} = \{A \vdash p \mid \exists R \subseteq \mathcal{R} : A \vdash_R p\}$ and attack relation $(A \vdash p, A' \vdash p') \in R$ iff $p \in \bar{A}'$.

The translation preserves the semantics [Schulz and Toni, 2017], the correspondence is 1:1 for all considered semantics.

Proposition 3.8. Let D be an ABAF with AF F_D , $\sigma \in \{gr, co, pr, st\}$. If $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$ then $(\{A \vdash p \mid A \in in(\lambda)\}, \{A \vdash p \mid \exists a \in A : a \in out(\lambda)\}, \{A \vdash p \mid \exists a \in A : a \in und(\lambda), A \cap out(\lambda) = \emptyset\}) \in \Lambda_\sigma(F)$; if $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(F)$ then $(in(\lambda|_{\mathbb{A}}), out(\lambda|_{\mathbb{A}}), und(\lambda|_{\mathbb{A}})) \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$.

Each AF induces an ABAF by associating assumptions and arguments [Toni, 2012]. The translation preserves semantics.

Definition 3.9. For an AF $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$, we define the ABAF $D_F = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \neg)$ s.t. $\mathcal{A} = \mathbb{A}$, and $\bar{a} \leftarrow b \in \mathcal{R}$ iff $(b, a) \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proposition 3.10. Let F be an AF, D_F its associated ABAF, and $\sigma \in \{co, pr, gr, st\}$. Then, $\Lambda_\sigma(F) = \Lambda_\sigma(D_F)$.

3.2 Conditional Independence

A dependency model I over a set of variables V is a ternary relation over disjoint subsets of V . We write $X \perp_I Y \mid Z$ iff $(X, Y, Z) \in I$ and say X and Y are independent, given Z [Pearl and Paz, 1986]. We drop I if clear from context.

We recall semi-graphoid axioms [Pearl, 2009]:

Symmetry $A \perp B \mid C \Rightarrow B \perp A \mid C$

Decomposition $A \perp B \cup B' \mid C \Rightarrow A \perp B \mid C$

Weak Union $A \perp B \cup B' \mid C \Rightarrow A \perp B \mid C \cup B'$

Contraction $A \perp B \mid C \wedge A \perp B' \mid C \cup B \Rightarrow A \perp B \cup B' \mid C$

For a DAG, the notion of *d-separation* introduces a dependency model which is a semi-graphoid; also, checking *d-separation* is in P [Darwiche, 2009]. A node $v = v_i$ in path $v_1 \dots v_n$ is a collider iff $(v_{i-1}, v_i), (v_{i+1}, v_i) \in E$.

Definition 3.11. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a DAG and $A, B, C \subseteq V$. Then, A and B are *d-separated*, given C ($A \perp_d B \mid C$) in G , iff for all undirected paths p between A and B , it holds that p contains a collider v s.t. $(\{v\} \cup DD_G(v)) \cap C = \emptyset$ or $C \cap \{v \in p \mid v \text{ is not a collider}\} \neq \emptyset$.

Rienstra *et al.* [2020] introduce independence for AFs.

Definition 3.12. For an AF $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$, semantics σ and disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ we say A is σ -independent of B , given C in F , written $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$, iff, for all $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \Lambda_\sigma(F)$, if $\lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C$ then there is some $\lambda_3 \in \Lambda_\sigma(F)$ s.t. $\lambda_3|_A = \lambda_1|_A$, $\lambda_3|_B = \lambda_2|_B$ and $\lambda_3|_C = \lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C$.

4 Independence in ABA

We investigate a semantical notion of conditional independence between assumptions. Similar to [Rienstra *et al.*, 2020; Darwiche, 1997], we base our notion on the acceptance status of assumptions. Intuitively, two sets of assumptions A and B are independent of each other, given a third set C , if coming to know the acceptance status of A in addition to knowing the acceptance status of C does not influence the acceptance status of B .

Definition 4.1. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, σ be a semantics, and let $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ be disjoint sets of assumptions. Then A is σ -independent of B , given C in D , written $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$, iff, for all labellings $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \Lambda_{\sigma}(D)$, if $\lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C$ then there is some labelling $\lambda_3 \in \Lambda_{\sigma}(D)$ s.t. $\lambda_3|_A = \lambda_1|_A$, $\lambda_3|_B = \lambda_2|_B$ and $\lambda_3|_C = \lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C$.

We drop σ and write $A \perp B \mid C$, if clear from context. By I_{σ} we denote the corresponding dependency model.

Example 4.2. The ABAF D from Example 3.2 has five co-labellings; four of them are preferred and stable:

σ -lab	a	b	c	d	w	k
co, gr	und	und	und	und	und	und
co, pr, st	in	in	out	out	in	out
co, pr, st	in	out	in	out	in	out
co, pr, st	out	in	in	out	in	in
co, pr, st	out	out	out	in	out	in

We can infer several (in)dependencies here.

- The assumptions a and b are σ -independent wrt. \emptyset for $\sigma \in \{pr, st\}$. For this, we identify the labels which are individually assigned to a and b under σ and verify that each combination of them is realized under σ .
- a and b are not co-independent, though: assigning a the label in and b the label und is individually possible, but there is no labelling with $\lambda(a) = in$ and $\lambda(b) = und$.
- When conditioning on $\{d\}$, the assumptions a and b are dependent under pr and st semantics. If $\lambda(d) = out$, then a and b can be individually out , but not together.

Our first central result sheds light on the close connection between assumption independence and independence between arguments (cf. [Rienstra et al., 2020]). We show that two sets of assumptions A, B are independent, given C , iff their corresponding assumption arguments are. Below, we identify assumption argument $\{a\} \vdash a$ with assumption a .

Proposition 4.3. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, F_D its corresponding AF, and let $\sigma \in \{co, gr, pr, st\}$. Then, for all $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we have $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$ in D iff $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$ in F_D .

Example 4.4. Consider the ABAF from Example 4.2. We obtain an AF F_D with assumption arguments $x_v : \{v\} \vdash v$ for $v \in \{a, b, c, d, w, k\}$ and rule-based arguments

$$x_{\bar{k}} : \{a\} \vdash \bar{k} \quad x_{\bar{a}} : \{b, c\} \vdash \bar{a} \quad x_{\bar{b}} : \{a, c\} \vdash \bar{b} \quad x_{\bar{c}} : \{a, c\} \vdash \bar{c}$$

$$x_{\bar{w}} : \{d\} \vdash \bar{w} \quad \forall v \in \{a, b, c\} : x_{\bar{v}}^d : \{d\} \vdash \bar{v} \quad x_{\bar{v}}^v : \{v\} \vdash \bar{v}$$

We have $(x, y) \in R$ iff $x = A \vdash p, y = B \vdash q$, and for some $b \in B : \bar{b} = p$. We depict the corresponding AF F_D below.

By Proposition 4.3 we can use the AF labellings to check for independence between assumptions; e.g., since x_k and x_a are pr -dependent in F_D , k and a are pr -dependent in D .

As a consequence, we can transfer results from the AF literature [Rienstra et al., 2020] to our setting. We so obtain that our independence notion for ABA is a semi-graphoid.

Proposition 4.5. σ -independence in ABA is a semi-graphoid.

Since each AF induces an ABAF [Toni, 2012] we can transfer ABA independence results to AFs as well.

Proposition 4.6. Let $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$ be an AF, D_F its associated ABAF, and $\sigma \in \{co, gr, pr, st\}$. Then, for all $A, B, C \subseteq \mathbb{A}$, we have $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$ in F iff $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$ in D_F .

In what follows, we assume an arbitrary but fixed ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$. First, note that under gr semantics, all sets are independent since the gr -labelling is unique. Next, we show that two assumption sets are independent when conditioned on a set that uniquely defines one of them.

Definition 4.7. Assumption set $A \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ σ -defines $B \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ iff for all partial σ -compatible labellings λ_A of A , there is a unique labelling λ_B which is σ -compatible with D .

Proposition 4.8. Let $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ be disjoint sets of assumptions. If C σ -defines B then $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$.

As a corollary, we obtain that conditional independence is downwards closed wrt. set inclusion.

Corollary 4.9. $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$ implies $A' \perp_{\sigma} B' \mid C$ for any semantics σ and for all $A' \subseteq A, B' \subseteq B$.

In contrast to d-separation in DAGs (cf. Def. 3.11), it is, however, not possible to check independence between sets of assumptions by looking at the pairwise independence of their members. In Example 3.2, for instance, the singletons a, b, c are pairwise st -independent while $\{a, b\}$ and $\{c\}$ are not.

We conclude by showing that deciding independence can be computationally hard. In addition, we identify the complexity of the corresponding decision problem for AFs.

Proposition 4.10. Let \mathcal{C} denote the class of AFs/flat ABAFs. Deciding σ -independence in \mathcal{C} is Π_2^P -complete for $\sigma \in \{co, st\}$ and Π_3^P -complete for $\sigma = pr$.

5 SCC-driven Independence Checks

The goal of this section is to establish sound and computationally efficient criteria for checking independence for ABAFs. First, we make use of the close connection between AFs and ABAFs and apply the d-graph method for AFs by [Rienstra et al., 2020] to ABAFs (Section 5.1). It turns out, however, that the applicability of the approach is limited due to the specific structure of the instantiated AF. For the second approach, we first define and investigate *SCC-recursiveness* for ABA based on the dependency graph [Rapberger et al., 2022] in Section 5.2. Next, in Section 5.3, we show that the *SCC-Markov condition* [Rienstra et al., 2020] is satisfied by universal and SCC-recursive ABA semantics, thereby providing the prerequisites for an independence check in ABAFs.

In each of these sections, SCCs will play an important part.

Definition 5.1. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a directed graph, $N \subseteq V$. N is a strongly connected component (SCC) of G iff for all $u, v \in N$ there is a path from u to v and N is \subseteq -maximal with this property. $SCC(G)$ denotes the set of all SCCs in G .

The SCCs of G induce a DAG $C_G = (SCC(G), \{(S, T) \mid S \subseteq PA_G(T)\})$. We call an SCC an *initial SCC* if it has no parents and a *terminal SCC* if it has no children in C_G .

5.1 AF-Based d-Graph Approach for ABA

Rienstra *et al.* [2020] develop a sound method to check independence in polynomial time: they transform a given AF into a DAG where each node corresponds to an argument or an SCC and, for a given SCC node, outgoing arcs encode membership and incoming arcs its parents in the AF. We restate their definition of the *d-graph* below.

Definition 5.2. Given a directed graph $Q = (V, E)$, the d-graph $G_Q = (V_d, E_d)$ is a DAG with $V_d = V \cup \{s \mid S \in SCC(F)\}$; and $(u, v) \in E_d$ iff (i) $v \in V$, $u \in SCC(F)$ and $v \in u$ or (ii) $u \in V$, $v \in SCC(F)$ and $u \in PA_G(v)$.

This seems promising at first sight: by Proposition 4.3, we can instantiate an ABAF and use the d-graph approach on the AF to check for independence in ABAFs. Below, we identify assumptions with their corresponding nodes in the d-graph.

Theorem 5.3. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, F_D the corresponding AF, G_{F_D} the d-graph resulting from F_D , and let $\sigma \in \{pr, co\}$. Then, for disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ of assumptions, $A \perp_d B \mid C$ in G_{F_D} implies $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in D .

Example 5.4. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \neg)$ with $\mathcal{A} = \{a, b, c, d\}$, contraries $\bar{a} = b$, $\bar{b} = c$, $\bar{c} = d$, and rule $(\bar{b} \leftarrow a, d)$. The resulting AF F_D is given below (with $x = \{a, d\} \vdash b$):

We have three SCCs: $S_1 = \{a\}$, $S_2 = \{b, x\}$, $S_3 = \{c, d\}$. From the d-graph approach, we obtain the following DAG:

We can use the DAG to identify independencies between assumptions: for given sets of assumptions A, B, C , check if C d-separates A and B ; e.g., since b cuts the path between a and c , we infer $\{a\} \perp_\sigma \{c\} \mid \{d\}$, $\sigma \in \{pr, co\}$, in the ABAF.

To avoid the exponential blow-up of the AF instantiation, we can utilize the poly-sized, polynomial-time computable, and (under projection) semantics-preserving *AF-sensitive instantiation* ([Lehtonen *et al.*, 2023], cf. Def. D.5)

Proposition 5.5. Checking independence in ABA using the d-graph approach on its AF-sensitive instantiation is in P.

Note that we require an SCC-structure which is informative enough. The SCCs that contain assumption arguments are however often either terminal or initial SCCs (cf. Proposition D.2). In an ABAF with separated contraries, i.e., if $\mathcal{A} \cap \bar{\mathcal{A}} = \emptyset$, conditioning on a set C cannot make assumption sets independent if they are not independent already.

Proposition 5.6. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, $\mathcal{A} \cap \bar{\mathcal{A}} = \emptyset$, F_D its corresponding AF, and G_{F_D} the resulting d-graph. Then, for all disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, if $A \perp_{I_D} B \mid C$ in G_{F_D} then $A \perp_d B \mid C'$ in G_{F_D} for all assumption sets $C' \supseteq C$.

Indeed, in case of our initial example not much can be said.

Example 5.7. In the associated AF F_D of the ABAF D from Example 4.2, all assumptions are terminal SCCs. When applying the d-graph approach, we get a DAG where all nodes that correspond to assumptions are connected with collider-free paths. Also, we cannot use assumptions to d-separate them; thus, $A \not\perp_d B \mid C$ for all assumption sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.

In the next two subsections, we propose a native SCC-based method for ABAFs that circumvents the AF instantiation by exploiting the attack structure of the ABAF directly.

5.2 SCC-Recursiveness for ABA

We explore the notion of *SCC-recursiveness* in ABA. In our context, we first need to clarify what the SCCs of an ABAF are. For this, we make use of the dependency graph [Rapberger *et al.*, 2022].

Definition 5.8. The dependency graph $P_D = (V, E, l)$ for an ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ is an edge-labelled graph with $V = \mathcal{L}$; and edge $e = (s, t) \in E$ iff (i) there is some rule $r \in \mathcal{R}$ with $s \in \text{body}(r)$ and $\text{head}(r) = \{t\}$, in this case $l(e) = +$; or (ii) $t \in \mathcal{A}$ and $\bar{t} = s$, in this case, $l(e) = -$.

Example 5.9. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF with $\mathcal{A} = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4\}$, and the following rules:

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} \bar{t}_1 \leftarrow t_2 & \bar{t}_2 \leftarrow t_1 & \bar{t}_2 \leftarrow t_3 & \bar{t}_3 \leftarrow t_1, t_2 & \bar{t}_3 \leftarrow t_3 \\ \bar{s}_1 \leftarrow s_2 & \bar{s}_2 \leftarrow s_3 & \bar{s}_2 \leftarrow t_1 & \bar{s}_3 \leftarrow t_1, t_2 & \bar{s}_3 \leftarrow s_4, t_3 \\ & & \bar{s}_4 \leftarrow t_3 & \bar{s}_4 \leftarrow s_3, t_2 & \bar{s}_4 \leftarrow s_1, s_2 \end{array}$$

Then the dependency graph P_D is given below.

Definition 5.10. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF with dependency graph P_D . The SCCs of D are given by

$$SCC(D) = \{N \cap \mathcal{A} \mid N \text{ is SCC of } P_D, N \cap \mathcal{A} \neq \emptyset\}.$$

For $S, T \in SCC(D)$, T is a parent of S iff there is a directed path $T_1 \dots T_n$ of SCCs from T to S in C_{P_D} s.t. $T_1 = T$, $T_n = S$ and $T_i = \emptyset$ for $i \notin \{1, n\}$.

Let us delve into the concepts needed to understand SCC-recursiveness in ABA. SCC-recursive semantics can be computed locally, starting from the initial SCCs. In what follows, we will go through such a recursion step by step, using Example 5.9, and introduce all required concepts along the way.

Example 5.11 (Ex. 5.9, cont.). Our ABAF D from before has two SCCs: $S = \{s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4\}$ and $T = \{t_1, t_2, t_3\}$. Here, T is an initial SCC, the (unique) parent SCC of S .

In the first step, we compute all σ -labellings for the single initial SCC T . If a given SCC has no parents, the computation amounts to evoking a so-called base function that returns all

its σ -labellings. Let $\sigma = co$. We obtain two labellings λ_1 and λ_2 with $\lambda_1(t_i) = und$, $i \leq 3$, and $\lambda_2(t_1) = in$, $\lambda_2(t_2) = out$, $\lambda_2(t_3) = und$. We continue with labelling $\lambda = \lambda_2$.

When computing the labellings for a non-initial SCC, the first step is to partition its elements based on the incoming arcs of the parent SCCs. In contrast to AFs, we can have attacks where the attacking assumption set consists both of assumptions from the parent and the current SCC, similar as in SCC-recursiveness for SETAFs [Nielsen and Parsons, 2006], cf. [König et al., 2022; Dvorák et al., 2024]. Before coming up with a suitable partition of the assumptions in a given SCC, we will first partition the rules accordingly.

Definition 5.12. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, $A \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ an assumption set and $\lambda : A \rightarrow L$ a labelling. A rule $r \in \mathcal{R}$ is

deactivated, $r \in \mathcal{R}_d(\lambda)$ iff $\lambda(a_i) = out$
for some assumption $a_i \in body(r) \cap A$

semi-active, $r \in \mathcal{R}_s(\lambda)$ iff $\lambda(a_i) = und$
for some assumption $a_i \in body(r) \cap A$ and $r \notin \mathcal{R}_d(\lambda)$

active, $r \in \mathcal{R}_a(\lambda)$ iff r is neither deactivated nor semi-active.

We omit λ and write $\mathcal{R}_s, \mathcal{R}_a$ if it does not cause confusion.

Example 5.13 (Ex. 5.9, cont.). We now want to move on and compute S , based on the information we got from T . Labelling λ deactivates rules with (the out-labelled) t_2 in the body (first row); it renders non-deactivated rules using t_3 semi-active (second row); the rest is active (last row).

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} \bar{t}_1 \leftarrow t_2 & \bar{t}_3 \leftarrow t_1, t_2 & \bar{s}_3 \leftarrow t_1, t_2 & \bar{s}_4 \leftarrow s_3, t_2 & & & \\ \bar{t}_3 \leftarrow t_3 & \bar{t}_2 \leftarrow t_3 & \bar{s}_3 \leftarrow s_4, t_3 & \bar{s}_4 \leftarrow t_3 & & & \\ \bar{t}_2 \leftarrow t_1 & \bar{s}_1 \leftarrow s_2 & \bar{s}_2 \leftarrow s_3 & \bar{s}_4 \leftarrow s_1, s_2 & \bar{s}_2 \leftarrow t_1 & & \end{array}$$

We are ready to define the partition of S into *defeated*, *provisionally defeated*, and *undefeated* assumptions.

Definition 5.14. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, $S \in SCC(D)$, $\lambda : PA_D(S) \rightarrow L$ a labelling, and $\mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s$ sets of active and semi-active rules. An assumption $a \in S$ is

defeated, $a \in def_D(S, \lambda, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff $in(\lambda) \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a} \bar{a}$

provisionally defeated, $a \in prdef_D(S, \lambda, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff a is not defeated and $A \setminus (S \cup out(\lambda)) \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a \cup \mathcal{R}_s} \bar{a}$

undefeated, $a \in undef_D(S, \lambda, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff a is neither defeated nor provisionally defeated

These sets can be considered a pre-selection for a labelling on S . We define a provisional labelling λ_p on $S \cup PA_D(S)$.

Definition 5.15. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, $S \in SCC(D)$, $\lambda : PA_D(S) \rightarrow L$ a labelling, and $\mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s$ sets of (semi-)active rules. We define the partial provisional labelling $\lambda_p(S, \lambda, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s) : S \cup PA_D(S) \rightarrow L$ by

$$\begin{aligned} out(\lambda_p) &= def_D(S, \lambda, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s) \cup out(\lambda) \\ und(\lambda_p) &= prdef_D(S, \lambda, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s) \cup und(\lambda) \\ in(\lambda_p) &= undef_D(S, \lambda, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s) \cup in(\lambda) \end{aligned}$$

Example 5.16 (Ex. 5.9, cont.). In D , the assumption s_2 is defeated, s_4 is provisionally defeated, and $\{s_1, s_3\}$ are undefeated. We use this partition of S to extend λ : the so-obtained provisional labelling λ_p is given by $out(\lambda_p) = \{s_2, t_2\}$, $und(\lambda_p) = \{s_4, t_3\}$, and $in(\lambda_p) = \{t_1, s_1, s_3\}$.

To carry out the recursion on the given SCC S , we restrict our ABAF using λ_p . The restriction $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ contains only the provisionally defeated and undefeated assumptions of S ; to compute our new rule set, we first update \mathcal{R}_a and \mathcal{R}_s to get rid of rules that use defeated assumptions from S .

Definition 5.17. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF and $\lambda_p(S, \lambda, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ a provisional labelling for an SCC $S \in SCC(D)$, and (semi-)active rule sets $\mathcal{R}_a^{up}, \mathcal{R}_s^{up}$. We define

- the restriction $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p} = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}', \mathcal{A}', \neg)$ of D to S under λ_p ,
 $\mathcal{A}' = S \cap (in(\lambda_p) \cup und(\lambda_p))$
 $\mathcal{R}' = \{head(r) \leftarrow body(r) \setminus (A \setminus S) \mid r \in \mathcal{R}_a^{up} \cup \mathcal{R}_s^{up}\}$
 where $\mathcal{R}_s^{up} = ((\mathcal{R}_a(\lambda_p) \setminus \mathcal{R}_a^{up}) \cup \mathcal{R}_s(\lambda_p)) \cap (\mathcal{R}_a \cup \mathcal{R}_s)$
 and $\mathcal{R}_a^{up} = \mathcal{R}_a(\lambda_p) \cap \mathcal{R}_a$ are the updated sets of semi-active and active rules, respectively; and
- the restricted rule sets to S , λ_p are $\mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p} = \mathcal{R}' \setminus \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$
 and $\mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p} = \{head(r) \leftarrow body(r) \setminus (A \setminus S) \mid r \in \mathcal{R}_a^{up}\}$.

Example 5.18 (Ex. 5.9, cont.). Restriction $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ has assumptions s_1, s_3, s_4 . To compute \mathcal{R}' , we first update our rule sets:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} \mathcal{R}_s^{up} : & \bar{t}_3 \leftarrow t_3 & \bar{t}_2 \leftarrow t_3 & \bar{s}_3 \leftarrow s_4, t_3 & \bar{s}_4 \leftarrow t_3 & & \\ \mathcal{R}_a^{up} : & \bar{t}_2 \leftarrow t_1 & \bar{s}_2 \leftarrow s_3 & \bar{s}_2 \leftarrow t_1 & & & \end{array}$$

Now, \mathcal{R}' contains the updated (semi-)active rules where all for the restriction irrelevant assumptions, i. e., assumptions not contained in $\{s_1, s_3, s_4\}$, are removed from the bodies:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} \text{semi-active in } S : & \bar{t}_3 \leftarrow & \bar{t}_2 \leftarrow & \bar{s}_3 \leftarrow s_4 & \bar{s}_4 \leftarrow & & \\ \text{active in } S : & \bar{t}_2 \leftarrow & \bar{s}_2 \leftarrow s_3 & \bar{s}_2 \leftarrow & & & \end{array}$$

Now, without further knowledge about which of the rules are semi-active only, we could come to the false conclusion that s_3 can be accepted because s_4 is attacked by a fact (i. e., by \emptyset). However, the rule ($s_4 \leftarrow$) is semi-active because it had an und-labelled assumption in its body, meaning that it cannot be counted as a successful attack against s_4 . We thus remember the restricted rule sets $\mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ and $\mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ (corresp. to the semi-active resp. active rules in S) for the next recursion step.

$D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ has three SCCs: $S_1 = \{s_1\}$, $S_2 = \{s_3\}$, $S_3 = \{s_4\}$. Again, we start with the initial SCCs. Taking \mathcal{R}_s into account, we obtain label und for s_3 and s_4 , in for s_1 , out for s_2 . Together with λ , we thus get a co-labelling for D .

We are ready to state our definition for SCC-recursiveness. We use a function $GF(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$, that takes as parameters an ABAF D , a set of candidate assumptions E , sets of (semi-)active rules $\mathcal{R}_s, \mathcal{R}_a$ to compute a set of labellings on D . A semantics σ is SCC-recursive if GF can be computed locally on each SCC with a σ -specific base function BF .

Definition 5.19. A semantics σ satisfies SCC-recursiveness if there exists a local function $BF_\sigma(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ such that for every ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ we have $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$ iff $\lambda \in GF_\sigma(D, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \emptyset)$ where $\lambda \in GF_\sigma(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff

- if $|SCC(D)| = 1$, $\lambda \in BF_\sigma(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$

- otherwise, for each $S \in SCC(D)$, $\lambda|_S = \lambda'$ for some $\lambda' \in GF_\sigma(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$ on $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$, and $\lambda(s) = \text{out}$ for $s \in S \setminus D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$, for the partial provisional labelling $\lambda_p(S, \lambda|_{PA_D(S)}, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$.

We give our main result of this subsection. The σ -specific base functions are given at the end of Appendix E.

Theorem 5.20. *Each ABA semantics $\sigma \in \{co, pr, st, gr\}$ satisfies SCC-recursiveness.*

5.3 Direct d-Graph Approach for ABA

We propose a sound method to determine conditional independence that does not rely on the AF instantiation. The idea is to apply the d-graph approach to the SCCs of the dependency graph of an ABAF instead of the associated AF.

Definition 5.21. *The d-graph of an ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ is $G_D = G_{P_D}$ the d-graph wrt. its dependency graph P_D .*

Example 5.22. *Consider an ABAF D with assumptions a, b, c and rules $(\bar{a} \leftarrow a), (\bar{b} \leftarrow a), (\bar{c} \leftarrow b)$. Each assumption has its own SCC in P_D , thus, G_D is a simple chain:*

For the check, we now first compute the dependency graph P_D of the ABAF D , then build the d-graph G_D based on the SCCs of P_D , and, finally, use the d-separation criterion in G_D to check independence between sets of assumptions. To show soundness of the approach, we recall the crucial SCC-Markov property [Rienstra *et al.*, 2020], which generalizes the local Markov property (cf. Def. A.4).

Definition 5.23. *A dependency model I satisfies the SCC-Markov condition wrt. graph G iff, for all $S \in SCC(G)$, $S \perp_I ND_G(S) \mid PA_G(S)$.*

We call σ an SCC-Markovian semantics if I_σ satisfies the SCC-Markov condition wrt. P_D . To guarantee this property, we require σ to be SCC-recursive, universal ($\Lambda_\sigma(D) \neq \emptyset$ for all D), and admissible ($\text{in}(\lambda)$ is admissible for all $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$).

We provide a counterpart of [Rienstra *et al.*, 2020, Thm. 2].

Theorem 5.24. *If σ is SCC-recursive, admissible, and universal, then I_σ satisfies the SCC-Markov condition.*

Since co , gr , and pr are admissible, universal, and, by Theorem 5.20, also SCC-recursive, we conclude the following.

Corollary 5.25. *Each $\sigma \in \{co, pr, gr\}$ is SCC-Markovian.*

We show that the native ABA d-graph approach is sound: we can indeed use the d-separation criterion in d-graph G_D to check independence for SCC-Markovian ABA semantics.

Theorem 5.26. *Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF and σ be SCC-Markovian. Then, for disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ of assumptions, $A \perp_d B \mid C$ in G_D implies $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in D .*

The approach is in P since constructing P_D is linear in the size of D . Thus, we can check for σ -independence between assumptions in polynomial time for all except st semantics.

As it turns out, the native d-graph approach for ABAFs reveals different independencies than the AF-approach.

Example 5.27. *All assumptions of the d-graph G_{F_D} of AF F_D for ABAF D from Example 5.22 are in terminal SCCs.*

In G_{F_D} , we cannot say if a and c are independent, given b , since they are connected by a collider-free path not containing b . In contrast, b separates a and c in G_D depicted in Example 5.22. So, from G_D we can conclude $a \perp_\sigma c \mid b$ for all semantics σ which satisfy the conditions in Theorem 5.24.

As for AFs, all elements in the same SCC are dependent. As a result, we can only determine independence between assumptions from different SCCs. Thus, just like the AF-approach, the native ABA-approach is incomplete, i.e., not all independencies can be identified. That being said, the ABA d-graph approach still gives us information the AF-approach cannot procure, specifically for ABAFs with separated contraries. Finally, let us head back to our introductory example.

Example 5.28. *In the d-graph G_D for the ABAF D from Example 3.2, assumption d separates every undirected path from w to, e.g., a . Therefore $a \perp_\sigma w \mid d$ in D for $\sigma \in \{co, pr, gr\}$.*

6 Summary and Conclusion

We have conducted a comprehensive study of a semantical notion for conditional independence between assumptions in flat ABA, including satisfaction of semi-graphoid axioms, results on computational complexity and two methods for a sound check of independence in polynomial time, the latter based on our novel notion of SCC-recursiveness for ABA. The proposed independence model is based on three-valued labellings, a choice which was motivated by promising results for a similar notion in the setting of abstract argumentation [Rienstra *et al.*, 2020]. Other concepts of independence between assumptions are feasible, though. In particular, defining independence wrt. joint acceptability of assumptions instead proved to be a well-behaved notion in a preliminary analysis which is beyond the scope of this paper. Diametric to this future work direction, ABA frameworks offer rich structural aspects, and investigating independence between literals, rules and independence in dynamic settings, also for non-flat ABA, are natural next steps. Specifically, our approach could empower enforcement methods as well as repairing and forgetting research [Rapberger and Ulbricht, 2023; Rapberger and Ulbricht, 2024; Berthold *et al.*, 2023] by enabling the decomposition of global reasoning tasks into local reasoning tasks in smaller instances. The high computational complexity of deciding independence may prove challenging for these studies. Overcoming their inherent limitations when it comes to handling ABAFs with large SCCs we consider an interesting albeit possibly challenging research objective. Lastly, ABA is closely related to other forms of structured argumentation, the adaption of our results to other structured argumentation formalisms such as ASPIC⁺ [Modgil and Prakken, 2013] or defeasible logic programming [García and Simari, 2004] would be worth investigating.

Ethical Statement

There are no ethical issues.

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A Extended Background

In this section, we give definitions for admissible semantics and further definitions used to prove our results.

A.1 Admissible Semantics

Within the scope of this appendix we define labelling-based admissible semantics in ABA [Schulz and Toni, 2017].

Definition A.1. $\lambda : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow L$ is an admissible labelling (abbr. ad-labelling) of $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \bar{\cdot})$ iff for each $a \in \mathcal{A}$,

- if $\lambda(a) = in$ then for all $B \vdash \bar{a}$, there is $b \in B$ s.t. $\lambda(b) = out$;
- $\lambda(a) = out$ iff there is $B \vdash \bar{a}$ s.t. $\lambda(b) = in$ for all $b \in B$;
- if $\lambda(a) = und$ then for all $B \vdash \bar{a}$ there is $b \in B$ s.t. $\lambda(b) \neq in$.

We denote by $\Lambda_{ad}(D)$ the set of all admissible labellings of the ABAF D .

For AFs, we use here the so-called *committed admissible labellings* [Schulz and Toni, 2017] where all attacked arguments are labelled out (this is not enforced in the original definition).

Definition A.2. $\lambda : \mathbb{A} \rightarrow L$ is a (comitted) admissible labelling (abbr. ad-labelling) of an AAF $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$ iff for each $a \in \mathbb{A}$,

- if $\lambda(a) = in$ then for all $b \in \mathbb{A}$, $(b, a) \in \mathbb{R}$ it holds that $\lambda(b) = out$;
- $\lambda(a) = out$ iff there is $b \in \mathbb{A}$, $(b, a) \in \mathbb{R}$ s.t. $\lambda(b) = in$
- if $\lambda(a) = und$ then for all $b \in \mathbb{A}$, $(b, a) \in \mathbb{R}$ it holds that $\lambda(b) \neq in$.

We denote by $\Lambda_{ad}(D)$ the set of all ad labellings of D .

Where we talk about admissible labellings on AFs, we refer to the committed admissible labellings.

The following correspondence result which subsumes **Proposition 3.8** is due to [Schulz and Toni, 2017].

Proposition A.3. Given an ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \bar{\cdot})$, its corresponding AF F and a semantics $\sigma \in \{ad, gr, co, pr, st\}$. If $\lambda \in \Lambda_{\sigma}(D)$ then there is $\lambda' \in \Lambda_{\sigma}(F)$ with

$$in(\lambda') = \{A \vdash p \mid A \in in(\lambda)\}$$

$$out(\lambda') = \{A \vdash p \mid \exists a \in A : a \in out(\lambda)\}$$

$$und(\lambda') = \{A \vdash p \mid \exists a \in A : a \in und(\lambda), A \cap out(\lambda) = \emptyset\}$$

For $\lambda \in \Lambda_{\sigma}(F)$, $(in(\lambda|_{\mathcal{A}}), out(\lambda|_{\mathcal{A}}), und(\lambda|_{\mathcal{A}})) \in \Lambda_{\sigma}(D)$.

For complete, grounded, stable, and preferred semantics, the correspondence between the labellings is one-to-one; for admissible semantics, the correspondence is one-to-many, i. e., an admissible AF labelling can correspond to multiple admissible ABA labellings.

A.2 More on Conditional Independence

We recall the local Markov condition.

Definition A.4. A dependency model I over V satisfies the local Markov condition with respect to a DAG $G = (V, E)$ iff for all $x \in V$, it holds that $\{v\} \perp_I ND_G(v) \mid PA_G(v)$.

Rienstra et al. (2020) show that the SCC-Markov condition implies the local Markov condition.

Below, we will generalise Definition 4.1 of conditional independence to arbitrary variables with potentially different sets of labels for each variable. For a set of variables V , let L_v denote v -specific labels for each $v \in V$. A labelling λ of V is a function that assigns each $v \in V$ some label in L_v . Let Λ denote a set of total labellings of V .

Definition A.5. Let V be a set of variables, Λ be a set of labellings of V , and let $A, B, C \subseteq V$ be disjoint sets of variables. Then V is independent of B , given C , in Λ , written $A \perp_{\Lambda} B \mid C$, iff, for all labellings $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \Lambda$, if $\lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C$ then there is some labelling $\lambda_3 \in \Lambda$ s.t. $\lambda_3|_A = \lambda_1|_A$, $\lambda_3|_B = \lambda_2|_B$ and $\lambda_3|_C = \lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C$.

Each Λ induces a dependency model I_{Λ} over V (we drop the subscript if clear from context). We will make use of this generalized independence definition in the proof of Theorem 5.26 (cf. Appendix F). For this, we will furthermore use the following result.

Verma and Pearl (1988) show, if I is a semi-graphoid over a set of variables V that satisfies the local Markov condition with respect to a DAG G , then d-separation in G implies independence wrt. I .

Theorem A.6. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a DAG, I a semi-graphoid over X that satisfies the local Markov condition with respect to G then $A \perp_d B \mid C$ implies $A \perp_I B \mid C$, for all disjoint $A, B, C \subseteq X$.

Moreover, checking independence in a DAG using d-separation is in P [Darwiche, 2009].

Lemma A.7. For a DAG $G = (V, E)$ and node sets $A, B, C \subseteq V$, checking $A \perp_d B \mid C$ is in P.

A.3 Graphical Representations

For our complexity proofs in Appendix C, we recall a graphical representation of ABAF. AFs with collective attacks (SETAFs) [Nielsen and Parsons, 2006] are ideally suited to depict the attack structure between the assumptions, as recently outlined [König et al., 2022]. SETAFs generalize AFs by allowing for collective attacks, depicted by joint arrows. A SETAF $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$ is a tuple consisting of abstract arguments \mathbb{A} and attacks $\mathbb{R} \subseteq 2^{\mathbb{A}} \times \mathbb{A}$. We recall the translation [König et al., 2022].

Definition A.8. The associated SETAF $H_D = (A, R)$ of an ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \bar{\cdot})$ is given by $A = \mathcal{A}$ and attack relation $(S, a) \in R$ iff $S' \vdash_{\mathcal{R}} \bar{a}$ for some $S' \subseteq S$.

Example A.9. Consider an ABAF with assumptions a, b, c , their contraries $\bar{a} = s$, $\bar{b} = p$, $\bar{c} = q$, and rules $(p \leftarrow a, c)$ and $(s \leftarrow c)$. We obtain the following arguments:

$$\{a\} \vdash a \quad \{b\} \vdash b \quad \{c\} \vdash c \quad u = \{a, c\} \vdash p \quad v = \{c\} \vdash s$$

Here, u and v are rule-induced arguments. We can represent the ABAF as an AF (left) and an SETAF (right) as follows:

The AF (left) contains all arguments, depicted as black circles with gray background, and the attacks between them (the assumption arguments are called a, b, c , respectively).

The SETAF (right) depicts the attack structure between the assumptions: a and c collectively attack b as $\{a, c\} \vdash p$, depicted as joint arc; and c attacks a since $\{c\} \vdash s$.

B Omitted Proofs and Observations of Section 4

Proposition 4.3. *Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, F_D its corresponding AF, and let $\sigma \in \{co, gr, pr, st\}$. Then, for all $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we have $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in D iff $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in F_D .*

Proof. Recall that we associate assumption arguments with their assumptions.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in D . Consider AF labellings $\lambda_A, \lambda_B, \lambda_C$ for the assumption arguments corresponding to A, B , and C , respectively, in F_D , and suppose $\lambda_A \cup \lambda_C$ and $\lambda_B \cup \lambda_C$ can be extended to full σ -labellings λ_1 and λ_2 in F_D , respectively. By Theorem 3.8, λ_1 and λ_2 projected to the assumption arguments corresponding to \mathcal{A} , are σ -labellings in D . Thus, there is some λ_3 that extends $\lambda_A \cup \lambda_B \cup \lambda_C$ to a σ -labelling in the ABAF D . Using Theorem 3.8 again, we obtain that $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in F_D .

(\Leftarrow) Suppose $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in F_D . Consider ABA labellings $\lambda_A, \lambda_B, \lambda_C$ for A, B, C in D , and suppose there exist σ -labellings λ_1, λ_2 that extend $\lambda_A \cup \lambda_C$ and $\lambda_B \cup \lambda_C$ in D . By Theorem 3.8 we can extend these labellings to AF labellings. Note that the assumption labellings coincide with the corresponding assumption argument labellings. By our initial assumption $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in F_D we thus obtain a labelling for $\lambda_A \cup \lambda_B \cup \lambda_C$ which we can project onto the assumptions, showing that there exists a labelling for $A \cup B \cup C$ in D . We have shown that $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in D . \square

Proposition 4.5. *σ -independence in ABA is a semi-graphoid.*

Proof. This follows from the correspondence shown in Proposition 4.3, for the interested reader we include a detailed proof below.

Symmetry Clear from Definition.

Decomposition Let λ_a be the partial labelling $\lambda_1|_A$ on A for some σ -labelling λ_1, λ_b likewise for λ_2 , such that $\lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C = \lambda_c$. Then the restriction of λ_2 to $B \cup B'$ yields a partial labelling $\lambda' = \lambda_2|_{B \cup B'}$ for which $\lambda'|_B = \lambda_b$. Furthermore, since A is independent of $B \cup B'$ given C there exists a σ -labelling λ_3 such that $\lambda_3|_A = \lambda_a, \lambda_3|_{B \cup B'} = \lambda'$ and $\lambda_3|_C = \lambda_c$. It follows that $\lambda_3|_B = (\lambda_3|_{B \cup B'})|_B = \lambda'_B = \lambda_b$ and therefore λ_3 realizes λ_a, λ_b and λ_c together. Since λ_1, λ_2 were chosen arbitrarily, we have A is independent of B given C .

Weak Union Let λ_1, λ_2 be σ -labellings which coincide on $C \cup B'$, i.e., $\lambda_1|_{C \cup B'} = \lambda_2|_{C \cup B'}$. Then also $\lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C$. Furthermore $\lambda_2|_{B \cup B'}$ is a partial labelling that can be realized together with $\lambda_2|_C$, namely via λ_2 . It follows from $A \perp B \cup B' \mid C$ that there exists an λ_3 with $\lambda_3|_A = \lambda_1|_A, \lambda_3|_{B \cup B'} = \lambda_2|_{B \cup B'}$ and $\lambda_3|_C =$

$\lambda_1|_C$. Furthermore, due to our definition of λ_2 it follows that $\lambda_3|_{C \cup B'} = \lambda_2|_{C \cup B'}$ and $\lambda_3|_B = (\lambda_3|_{B \cup B'})|_B = (\lambda_2|_{B \cup B'})|_B = \lambda_2|_B$. Thus, $A \perp B \mid C \cup B'$.

Contraction Let λ_1, λ_2 be σ -labellings which coincide on C , i.e., $\lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C$. Since $A \perp B \mid C$, there exists some λ' such that $\lambda'|_A = \lambda_1|_A, \lambda'|_B = \lambda_2|_B$ and $\lambda'|_C = \lambda_1|_C$. Now, since $A \perp B' \mid C \cup B$, for λ' and λ_2 there exists some λ_3 such that $\lambda_3|_A = \lambda'|_A = \lambda_1|_A, \lambda_3|_B = \lambda_2|_B$ and $\lambda_3|_{C \cup B} = \lambda_2|_{C \cup B}$. Thus, we also have $\lambda_3|_C = \lambda_2|_C$ and $\lambda_3|_{B \cup B'} = \lambda_2|_{B \cup B'}$. Since λ_1, λ_2 were chosen arbitrarily, we have $A \perp B \cup B' \mid C$. \square

Proposition 4.6. *Let $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R})$ be an AF, D_F its associated ABAF, and $\sigma \in \{co, gr, pr, st\}$. Then, for all $A, B, C \subseteq \mathbb{A}$, we have $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in F iff $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in D_F .*

Proof. The result follows from the 1-1 correspondence between semantics for AF F and its corresponding ABAF D_F . \square

Proposition 4.8. *Let $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ be disjoint sets of assumptions. If C σ -defines B then $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$.*

Proof. Let $\lambda_C, \lambda_A, \lambda_B$ denote partial labellings of C, A, B , and let λ_1 and λ_2 be labellings s.t. $\lambda_1|_C = \lambda_2|_C = \lambda_C, \lambda_1|_B = \lambda_B$, and $\lambda_2|_A = \lambda_A$. By assumption C σ -defines B , we obtain $\lambda_2|_B = \lambda_B$ and thus $\lambda_2|_V = \lambda_V$ for all $V \in \{A, B, C\}$. \square

C Complexity results (Proof of Proposition 4.10)

In this section, we prove the following result.

Proposition 4.10. *Let \mathcal{C} denote the class of AFs/flat ABAFs. Deciding σ -independence in \mathcal{C} is Π_2^P -complete for $\sigma \in \{co, st\}$ and Π_3^P -complete for $\sigma = pr$.*

Formally, we consider the following decision problem.

Ind_σ

Input: ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$, sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$

Output: TRUE iff $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in D .

We first give the proof for stable semantics.

Proposition C.1. *Ind_{st} is Π_2^P -complete.*

Proof. (Membership) We have to check whether for all σ -labellings λ_1, λ_2 , whose partial labellings on C coincide, there exists a σ -labelling λ_3 which coincides with λ_1 on A and C and with λ_2 on B (and C). The complement is the following:

Do there exist σ -labellings λ_1, λ_2 such that there is no λ_3 with the aforementioned properties?

We can guess such λ_1, λ_2 , check in P that they are indeed σ -labellings, and then check with a call to an NP -oracle that there is no σ -labelling λ_3 that coincides with λ_1 on A and C and with λ_2 on B (and C).

(Hardness)

Figure 1: SETAF representation (cf. Appendix A.3) of the Reduction used in Proposition C.1 for a formula $\forall A \exists Y \varphi$ where φ is given by the clauses $\{\{x_0, x_2, y_1\}, \{x_0, \bar{x}_2, \bar{y}_1, \bar{x}_1\}, \{x_0, \bar{x}_2, x_1\}\}$.

We reduce from QBF_{\forall}^2 . For the proof we reduce the problem of deciding whether a formula $\Psi = \forall X \exists Y \varphi$ with φ a CNF over variables $X \cup Y$ given by clauses cl_1, \dots, cl_l is valid to σ -independence between the two assumption sets $\{\varphi\}$ and $\{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ (the conditioning set is the empty set). Wlog, we can assume that X contains an atom x_0 which is contained in each cl_i .

To be more precise, we show that Ψ is valid iff the sets $\{\varphi\}$ and $\{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ are independent given the empty set. The ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \bar{\cdot})$ for the reduction is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A} &= \{x_0, \dots, x_n, \bar{x}_0, \dots, \bar{x}_n, y_1, \dots, y_m, \bar{y}_1, \dots, \bar{y}_m, cl_1, \dots, cl_l, \varphi, t\} \\ \mathcal{L} &= \mathcal{A} \cup \{a_c \mid a \in \mathcal{A}\} \\ \bar{a} &= a_c \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A} \end{aligned}$$

with rules

$$\begin{array}{lll} \varphi_c \leftarrow t & \varphi_c \leftarrow cl_i & t_c \leftarrow \varphi \\ (x_i)_c \leftarrow \bar{x}_i & (\bar{x}_i)_c \leftarrow x_i & (cl_i)_c \leftarrow x_0 \\ (y_i)_c \leftarrow \bar{y}_i & (\bar{y}_i)_c \leftarrow y_i & \end{array}$$

and $(cl_i)_c \leftarrow a$ iff a occurs in clause i of φ for all $a \in \{x_0, \dots, x_n, \bar{x}_0, \dots, \bar{x}_n, y_1, \dots, y_m, \bar{y}_1, \dots, \bar{y}_m\}$.

Note that the (SET)AF-instantiation (cf. Appendix A.3) is not necessary to compute independence, the semantics can be applied directly. For illustration, consider the (SET)AF depicted in Figure 1.

- Let Ψ be valid.

Consider an arbitrary partial labelling λ_1 (in out) on $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and an arbitrary labelling λ_2 (in out) of φ .

We construct the labelling λ_3 as follows: choose $\lambda_3(X)$ so that it matches the labelling λ_1 we fixed, ie $\text{in}(\lambda_1) \cap X = \text{in}(\lambda_3) \cap X$. By assumption Ψ is valid, so there is some (in,out)-labelling on Y so that φ can be labeled in. We can now choose freely between the in or out label for φ , since both $\text{in}(\lambda_3) = \{\bar{x}_0\} \cup \text{in}(X) \cup \{t\}$ and $\text{in}(\lambda_3) = \{\bar{x}_0\} \cup \text{in}(X) \cup \{\varphi\}$ are stable.

- Suppose Ψ not valid. Then there exists an assignment of X so that for all assignments of Y , φ is not true.

Let λ_1 be the (in,out)-labelling corresponding to the assignment of X . Let $\lambda_2(\varphi) = \text{in}$. Since x_0 exists

and attacks all c_i , this is possible. Now, λ_1 and λ_2 are separately realizable (ie exists extensions) but $\lambda_1 \cup \lambda_2$ not, since there is no labelling of Y such that all cl -assumptions are labeled out. \square

Proposition C.2. Ind_{σ} is Π_2^P -complete for $\sigma \in \{co, ad\}$.

Proof. (Membership) Analogously to the Membership Proof of Proposition C.1.

(Hardness)

For the hardness proof for co -independence we modify the above proof and reduce the problem of deciding whether a formula $\forall X \exists Y \varphi$ is valid for σ -independence between the two assumption sets $\{\varphi\}$ and $\{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ given the set $\{r_0, r_1, \dots, r_n\}$ as a condition; see Figure 2.

Note first, that the additional arguments are either labeled undecided or out, but never in, and that they are labeled out iff for each pair of $x_i, \neg x_i$ one is labeled in and the other out. Furthermore, for every complete labelling where one of the x -arguments is undecided, all x -arguments, all y -arguments and all r -arguments are undecided. Two labels for φ are compatible with the r -arguments being undecided, i.e., φ can be either undecided or out. And this remains true if the x -arguments are labeled undecided, which is the only possible label for the x -arguments under complete semantics when the r -arguments are labeled undecided. So we only have to consider whether the (in,out)-labellings on the x -arguments are compatible with any φ -label for the case where all r -arguments are labeled out. Below we repeat the argumentation for the case of stable semantics, which applies now.

- Ψ valid.

Consider an arbitrary labelling λ_1 (in out) of X and an arbitrary labelling λ_2 (in out) of φ .

We construct the extension E as follows: choose X so that it maps to the labelling we fixed, ie $\text{in}(X) \subseteq E$. By assumption Ψ is valid, there is some assignment of Y so that φ can be accepted. We can choose acceptability of φ accordingly, since $\{\bar{x}_0\} \cup \text{in}(X) \cup \{t\}$, $\{\bar{x}_0\} \cup \text{in}(X) \cup \{\varphi\}$ and $\{\bar{x}_0\} \cup \text{in}(X)$ (t, φ undecided) are complete.

- Ψ not valid. Then there exists an assignment of X so that for all assignments of Y , φ is not true.

Let λ_1 be the labelling corresponding to the assignment of X . Let $\lambda_2(\varphi) = \text{in}$. Since x_0 exists and attacks all c_i , this is possible. Now, λ_1 and λ_2 are separately realizable (ie exists extensions) but $\lambda_1 \cup \lambda_2$ not. \square

Proposition C.3. Ind_{pr} is Π_3^P -complete.

Proof. (Membership) The decision problem in question is the complement of the following:

Do there exist preferred labellings λ_1, λ_2 such that there is no preferred labelling λ_3 that coincides with λ_1 on A and C and with λ_2 on B (and C).

We can guess such λ_1, λ_2 , check in $coNP$ that they are indeed preferred labellings, and then check with a call to a Σ_2^P -oracle that there is no preferred labelling λ_3 that coincides with λ_1 on A and C and with λ_2 on B (and C). To see why we need a Σ_2^P -oracle, note that (the

Figure 2: SETAF representation (cf. Appendix A.3) of the Reduction used in Proposition C.2 for a formula $\forall A\exists Y\phi$ where ϕ is given by the clauses $\{\{x_0, x_2, y_1\}, \{x_0, \bar{x}_2, \bar{y}_1, \bar{x}_1\}, \{x_0, \bar{x}_2, x_1\}\}$.

Figure 3: SETAF representation (cf. Appendix A.3) of the Reduction used in Proposition C.3 for a formula $\exists X\forall Y\exists Z\phi$ being not valid where ϕ is given by the clauses $\{\{x_0, y_1, z_1\}, \{x_0, \bar{x}_2, \bar{z}_1, \bar{x}_1\}, \{x_0, \bar{y}_1, x_1\}\}$.

complement to) this check asks about the existence of such a preferred labelling λ_3 which could be done by guessing λ_3 , checking in *coNP* it is indeed preferred and checking in *P* it coincides with λ_1 and λ_2 on the sets in question.

(Hardness)

We show: $\Psi = \exists X\forall Y\exists Z\phi$ is not valid iff the two assumption sets $\{\phi\}$ and $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ are *pr*-independent given the empty set as a condition for the construction depicted in Figure 3. Wlog, we can assume that Y contains an atom y_0 contained in each clause cl_i .

We have assumptions $x_i, \bar{x}_i, y_i, \bar{y}_i, z_i, \bar{z}_i$ for each atom in the respective vectors X, Y, Z of the formula, which attack an assumption cl_i representing the i th-clause of ϕ , if they are contained in cl_i , and the clause assumptions in turn attack the assumption ϕ .

We introduce a back loop by having the z -arguments attacked from an assumption $\bar{\phi}$, which is in turn attacked by ϕ to ensure none of these assumptions can be assigned the label *in*, unless ϕ itself is labeled *in*.

The label *in* for ϕ can be realized through labelling the additional assumption y_0 *in*, which attacks all clause-assumptions, together with any assignment to the remaining x -, y - and z -assumptions as the set of *in*-labelled assumptions we get a preferred labelling with $\lambda(\phi) = \text{in}$.

The label *und* for ϕ can be realized through the additional assumption t , which attacks all x -assumptions, y -assumptions and z -assumptions, leaving the self-attacking clause-assumptions and all subsequent assumptions to be labeled *und*. We get a preferred labelling with $\lambda(\phi) = \text{und}$.

The label *out* for ϕ cannot be realized, since all attackers of ϕ are self-attackers.

Note that there is no preferred labelling which assigns the label *undecided* to any of the x - or y -assumptions due to maximality of the set of *in*-labelled assumptions under preferred semantics.

Ψ not valid. Consider an arbitrary labelling λ_1 (*in* *out*) of X .

We can realize the label $\lambda_2(\phi) = \text{und}$ for ϕ by labelling t *in*. We can also realize the label $\lambda'_2(\phi) = \text{in}$ by assigning y_0 the label *in* and t the label *out*. Note that we can do this for any labelling of the x -assumptions, so λ_1 and λ'_2 can be realized together. For independence it is left to show that there is a preferred labelling which realizes λ_1 and $\lambda_2(\phi) = \text{und}$ together. For any such labelling the z -assumptions would also be labeled *und*. Since Ψ is not valid, we know that for each x -assignment there exists a y -assignment such that for any z -assignment ϕ is not satisfied. Therefore we can choose a labelling λ_3 of the y -assumptions, such that there is no way to defend ϕ , and thus the z -assumptions, so in_{λ_3} is maximal while $\lambda_3(\phi) = \text{und}$ and therefore λ_3 is a preferred labelling. So λ_1 and λ_2 can indeed be realized together and thus $\{\phi\}$ and $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ are *pr*-independent.

Ψ valid. Then there exists an assignment of X so that for all assignments of Y there exists an assignment of Z , such that ϕ is satisfied.

Let λ_1 be the labelling corresponding to said assignment of X . Let $\lambda_2(\phi) = \text{und}$ (we can realize this using assumption t). Now, λ_1 and λ_2 are separately realizable (ie there exist corresponding preferred labellings) but $\lambda_1 \cup \lambda_2$ is not, since the set of *in*-labelled assumptions has to be maximal under preferred semantics and for any labelling of the y -assumptions we can find a labelling of the z -assumptions that forces us to add ϕ to the set of *in*-labelled arguments. Due to the back loop, any assignment to Z which does not result in ϕ being defended, renders all z -assumptions labeled *und*, so there is no other superset to the *in*-labelled x - and y -assumptions, which would exclude ϕ . Therefore there is no preferred labelling which realizes λ_1 and λ_2 together, so $\{\phi\}$ and $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ are not *pr*-independent. \square

The provided reductions also work for proving the hardness of deciding Independence in AFs. Here, we consider the following decision problem.

Ind_{σ}^{AF}

Input: AF $F = (\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{R}, \text{sets } A, B, C \subseteq \mathbb{A})$

Output: TRUE iff $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$ in F .

Proposition C.4. Ind_{σ}^{AF} is Π_2^P -complete for $\sigma \in \{co, st, ad\}$ and Π_3^P -complete for $\sigma = pr$.

Proof. (Membership) We can construct the associated ABAF D_F in polynomial time, then check independence in D_F (Proposition 4.6), thus Propositions C.1, C.2 and C.3 apply.

(Hardness) Instead of the ABAF used for the reduction to flat ABA, we can use the following AF-construction:

$$\mathbb{A} = \{x_0, \dots, x_n, \bar{x}_0, \dots, \bar{x}_n, y_1, \dots, y_m, \bar{y}_1, \dots, \bar{y}_m, cl_1, \dots, cl_l, \varphi, t\}$$

with attacks

$$\begin{array}{lll} \varphi \rightarrow t & cl_i \rightarrow \varphi & t \rightarrow \varphi \\ (x_i) \rightarrow \bar{x}_i & (\bar{x}_i) \rightarrow x_i & x_0 \rightarrow (cl_i)_c \\ (y_i) \rightarrow \bar{y}_i & (\bar{y}_i) \rightarrow y_i & \end{array}$$

and $a \rightarrow (cl_i)$ iff a occurs in clause i of φ for all $a \in \{x_0, \dots, x_n, \bar{x}_0, \dots, \bar{x}_n, y_1, \dots, y_m, \bar{y}_1, \dots, \bar{y}_m\}$.

Now the reasoning of the proof of Proposition C.1 applies to $\sigma = st$ on AFs. The constructions from Propositions C.2 and C.3 can be modified accordingly to prove hardness for $\sigma \in \{co, ad, pr\}$. \square

D Omitted Proofs of Subsection 5.1

Theorem 5.3. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, F_D the corresponding AF, G_{F_D} the d -graph resulting from F_D , and let $\sigma \in \{pr, co\}$. Then, for disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ of assumptions, $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$ in G_{F_D} implies $A \perp_{\sigma} B \mid C$ in D .

Proof. Follows from Proposition 4.3, and the following results in [Rienstra *et al.*, 2020]: Corollary 1 and Theorem 2, together with the fact that complete and preferred semantics are universal and SCC-decomposable [Baroni *et al.*, 2014] \square

Proposition 5.6. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, $\mathcal{A} \cap \bar{\mathcal{A}} = \emptyset$, F_D its corresponding AF, and G_{F_D} the resulting d -graph. Then, for all disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, if $A \perp_{ID} B \mid C$ in G_{F_D} then $A \perp_{d} B \mid C'$ in G_{F_D} for all assumption sets $C' \supseteq C$.

Proof. Suppose $A \perp_{d} B \mid C$ in G_{F_D} . Then there is an active path² between A and B given C . Let p denote an active path between A and B given C . Let $C' \supseteq C$ denote a superset of C . Note that C' cannot block p via a fork or a chain because C contains only terminal nodes, and each terminal node has incoming arcs only. Moreover, C contains a descendant of each collider in p . Thus, we obtain $A \perp_{d} B \mid C'$ in G_{F_D} . \square

Next, we give an example that the converse of Proposition 5.6 is not true.

²A path p between A and B is active given C iff for each collider v of p , C contains v or one of its descendants; and C contains no non-collider of p .

Example D.1. Consider an ABAF D with assumptions a, b, c and rules $(\bar{a} \leftarrow)$, $(\bar{b} \leftarrow)$, and $(\bar{c} \leftarrow a, b)$. In the corresponding d -graph G_{F_D} , the path between a and b contains a collider corresponding to the SCC $\{a, b\} \vdash \bar{c}$. It can be checked that when conditioning on c , a and b are dependent in G_{F_D} .

We furthermore show that many assumption SCCs are either terminal or initial.

Proposition D.2. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, F_D its associated AF, and $a \in \mathcal{A}$.

1. If $\bar{b} \neq a$ for all $b \in \mathcal{A}$, then $\{a\}$ is a terminal SCC;
2. if $\bar{a} \in \mathcal{A}$ and there are $b_1, \dots, b_n \in \mathcal{A}$, $\bar{b}_i = b_{i+1}$, $\bar{b}_n = a$, $\bar{a} = b_1$, then $a \in S$ for some initial SCC S .

Proof. 1. Let $a \in \mathcal{A}$ such that there is no $b \in \mathcal{A}$ with $\bar{b} = a$. By definition of the attack relation \mathbb{R} of F_D the argument $\{a\} \vdash a$ attacks only arguments $B \vdash p$ with $a \in \bar{B}$. So $\{a\} \vdash a$ has no outgoing attacks and consequently no path to any other argument. Thus $\{a\}$ is a terminal SCC of F_D .

2. Let the assumptions a, b_1, \dots, b_n each be the contrary of the designated other assumption as stated. Since D is flat, neither a nor any b_i can be head of a rule in \mathcal{R} , therefore $\{a\} \vdash a$ and $\{b_i\} \vdash b_i$ are the only arguments in F_D deriving any of these assumptions. Since the contrary of an assumption is unique, no other argument can derive \bar{a} resp. \bar{b}_i , so only the arguments $\{b_i\} \vdash b_i$ (and $\{a\} \vdash a$) itself have a path to a . Furthermore, for all b_i it holds that a has a path to b_i . Therefore $\{a, b_1, \dots, b_n\}$ is an initial SCC of F_D which contains a . \square

D.1 Keeping the AF instantiation small

Note that in general, the standard translation from ABAFs to AFs can yield exponentially many arguments [Lehtonen *et al.*, 2023]. To avoid the exponential blow up, Lehtonen *et al.* (2023) provide a transformation from an arbitrary ABAF D into a so-called *atomic ABAF* D' , where all rule bodies contain only assumptions. First, they translate a given ABAF D into a *non-circular ABAF* $D.4$ before they apply their main translation into an atomic ABAF. The instantiation from an atomic ABAF to an AF is linear since each rule yields exactly one argument.

Lehtonen *et al.* (2023) provide their results for extension-based semantics. We will thus recall complete, grounded, preferred, and stable extension-based ABA semantics (abbr. *co, gr, pr, st*). For a given ABAF D , for a set of assumptions E , we write $E \in ad(D)$ iff E is admissible in D .

Definition D.3. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF and let $S \in ad(D)$.

- $S \in co(D)$ iff S contains every assumption it defends;
- $S \in gr(D)$ iff S is \subseteq -minimal in $co(D)$;
- $S \in pr(D)$ iff S is \subseteq -maximal in $co(D)$;
- $S \in st(D)$ iff S attacks each $\{x\} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus S$.

We recall the translations from [Lehtonen *et al.*, 2023]. We take the definition of circular tree-based arguments (proof trees) from Craven and Toni (2016).

Definition D.4. A tree-based argument is circular if there is a path from a leaf to the root which contains two distinct vertices with the same label. An ABAF is circular if there is a circular tree-based argument for this framework. An ABAF is non-circular if it is not circular.

We start with the main translation from an non-circular ABAF into an atomic ABAF [Lehtonen *et al.*, 2023].

Definition D.5. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be a non-circular ABA framework such that each $s \in \mathcal{L}$ is in $Th_D(\mathcal{A})$. We define $D' = (\mathcal{L}', \mathcal{R}', \mathcal{A}', \neg')$ as the AF-sensitive ABA framework of D as follows. For each $s \in \mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{A}$

- let s_d and s_{nd} be two fresh assumptions, with
- $\overline{s_d} = s_{nd}$ and $\overline{s_{nd}} = s$ in \neg' .

Let $\mathcal{A}' = \mathcal{A} \cup \{s_d, s_{nd} \mid s \in \mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{A}\}$ and $\mathcal{L}' = \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{A}'$. The assumptions that are present in D have the same contraries in D' as in D . For each rule $r \in \mathcal{R}$, let r' be r except that if $body(r)$ contains a non-assumption s , replace s by s_d . Finally, set $\mathcal{R}' = \{r' \mid r \in \mathcal{R}\}$.

For an ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ and rule set $R \subseteq \mathcal{R}$, we let $Th_R(E) = Th_{D'}(E)$, for $D' = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}', \mathcal{A}, \neg)$.

In [Lehtonen *et al.*, 2023], it has been shown that the translation preserves extension-based semantics $\sigma \in \{co, pr, st\}$ under projection, i.e., for a non-circular ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ and its transformation D' , it holds that

- if $E \in \sigma(D)$, then there is an $E' \in \sigma(D')$ with $E = E' \cap \mathcal{A}$ and $Th_{\mathcal{R}}(E) = Th_{\mathcal{R}'}(E') \cap \mathcal{L}$, and
- if $E' \in \sigma(D')$, then $E' \cap \mathcal{A} \in \sigma(D)$ and $Th_{\mathcal{R}}(E) = Th_{\mathcal{R}'}(E') \cap \mathcal{L}$.

The result can be extended to non-circular ABAFs [Lehtonen *et al.*, 2023].

Definition D.6. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF. We define the non-circular ABA D° as follows. Let $k = |\mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{A}|$. For each atomic rule $r = s \leftarrow p_1, \dots, p_n$ in \mathcal{R} we consider k copies r_1, \dots, r_k of the form $r_i = s^i \leftarrow p_1, \dots, p_n$ with $s^k = s$. For each remaining rule $r = s \leftarrow p_1, \dots, p_n$ in \mathcal{R} we consider $k - 1$ copies r_2, \dots, r_k where for each $2 \leq j \leq k$: $head(r_j) = s^j$ with $s^k = s$, if $p_i \in \mathcal{A}$, then $p_i \in body(r_j)$, if $p_i \notin \mathcal{A}$, then $p_i^{j-1} \in body(r_j)$. We let $D^\circ = (\mathcal{L}^\circ, \mathcal{R}^\circ, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ where

$$\mathcal{L}^\circ = \mathcal{L} \cup \bigcup_{j=1}^k \{s^j \mid s \in \mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{A}\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{R}^\circ = \bigcup_{j=1}^k \{r^j \mid r \text{ atomic}\} \cup \bigcup_{j=2}^k \{r^j \mid r \text{ not atomic}\}.$$

The translation is semantics preserving, i.e., for an ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$, $\sigma(D) = \sigma(D^\circ)$ for each $\sigma \in \{ad, co, pr, gr, st\}$ [Lehtonen *et al.*, 2023].

We show that the transformations preserve labelling-based semantics.

Proposition D.7. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF and let $\sigma \in \{co, pr, st\}$.

1. Let D be non-circular and D' the resulting AF-sensitive ABAF. Then, if $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$ then there exists $\lambda' \in \Lambda_\sigma(D')$ with $\lambda'|_{\mathcal{A}} = \lambda$; and if $\lambda' \in \Lambda_\sigma(D')$ then $\lambda'|_{\mathcal{A}} \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$.
2. Let D° be the corresponding non-circular ABAF. Then, $\Lambda_\sigma(D) = \Lambda_\sigma(D^\circ)$.

Proof. 1. Let $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$. By the results from Lehtonen *et al.* 2023, there is an $E' \in \sigma(D')$ which extends $E = in(\lambda)$, i.e., $E = E' \cap \mathcal{A}$, and derives the same claims. Thus, E and E' attack the same assumptions. We let $in(\lambda') = E$, $out(\lambda') = E^+$, $und(\lambda') = \mathcal{A} \setminus (E \cup E^+)$. It holds that $\lambda'|_{\mathcal{A}} = \lambda$.

Now, let $\lambda' \in \Lambda_\sigma(D')$. Let $\lambda = \lambda'|_{\mathcal{A}}$. From the correspondence result by Lehtonen *et al.* 2023, we obtain $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$.

2. Let D° be the corresponding non-circular ABAF. As discussed above, we obtain the same arguments for D and D° , thus, we obtain $\Lambda_\sigma(D) = \Lambda_\sigma(D^\circ)$. \square

Proposition 5.5. Checking independence in ABA using the d-graph approach on its AF-sensitive instantiation is in P.

Proof. Given an ABAF D , compute the non-circular ABAF D° and apply the transformation into an AF-sensitive ABAF $(D^\circ)'$. We can then compute the corresponding AF in linear time (in the size of $(D^\circ)'$), since each rule induces a single argument. From the resulting AF, we can construct the corresponding d-graph in P [Rienstra *et al.*, 2020]. Moreover, checking whether two node sets in the resulting DAG are independent is in P. Thus, we have shown that the d-graph approach for checking independence in ABA with the AF-sensitive instantiation is in P. By Lemma D.7, the approach is sound. \square

E Omitted Proofs of Subsection 5.2

We will make use of the following notation: A derivation $A \vdash_R p$ of some $p \in \mathcal{L}$ from an assumption set A is called *deactivated*, if it uses at least one deactivated rule, *semi-active* if it uses only semi-active and active rules, and *active* otherwise.

We say $A \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ has an *active/semi-active/deactivated* attack on $a \in \mathcal{A}$ if there exists a derivation that uses active/only semi-active and deactivated/only deactivated derivation $A \vdash_R \bar{a}$.

Lemma E.1. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ a set of assumptions, $\mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ sets of active and semiactive rules, $\mathcal{R}_a \cup \mathcal{R}_s = \mathcal{R}$. Then $\lambda \in GF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff

- $\lambda \in \Lambda_{ad}(D)$ and
- $in(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and
- for every $a \in \mathcal{A}$ if $\lambda(a) = out$ then $in(\lambda) \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a} \bar{a}$.

Proof. We define the admissible base function $\lambda \in BF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff

- $in(\lambda) \subseteq E$
- $out(\lambda) = \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid in(\lambda) \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a} \bar{a}\}$
- $in(\lambda) \cap out(\lambda) = \emptyset$

- $\text{und}(\lambda) = \mathcal{A} \setminus (\text{in}(\lambda) \cup \text{out}(\lambda))$
- Let $B \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. If $B \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a \cup \mathcal{R}_s} \bar{a}$ for some $a \in \text{in}(\lambda)$, then $\text{in}(\lambda) \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a} \bar{b}$ for some $b \in B$.

In short, BF_{ad} determines all admissible labellings λ of D , where $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and only active attacks are used to defend against all active and semi-active attacks.

Proof by induction over the size of \mathcal{A} , in the base case $|\mathcal{A}| = 1$ we have $|SCC(D)| = 1$, for the induction step we distinguish two cases, $|SCC(D)| = 1$ or $|SCC(D)| > 1$.

($|SCC(D)| = 1$) By definition of SCC-Recursion we have $\lambda \in GF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff $\lambda \in BF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$. It follows directly from our definition of the base function that $\lambda \in BF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff λ satisfies all three items.

The base case is covered by this case, since we do not use the induction hypothesis.

($|SCC(D)| > 1$) We show that $\lambda \in \Lambda_{ad}(D), \text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and $\text{in}(\lambda)$ attacks every out-labelled assumption actively iff for every $S \in SCC(D)$ the partial labelling λ_S coincides on $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ with some

$$\lambda' \in GF_{ad}(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$$

and satisfies $\lambda(s) = \text{out}$ for all $s \in S \setminus D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ for $\lambda_p(S, \lambda_{PA_D(S)}, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ the partial provisional labelling of S .

(\Rightarrow) Let $\lambda \in \Lambda_{ad}(D)$. Since $S \setminus D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ is exactly the set of defeated arguments $\text{out}(\lambda_p)$, it is attacked by $E = \text{in}(\lambda)$, because λ is an admissible labelling, and therefore $\lambda(s) = \text{out}$ holds for all $s \in \text{out}(\lambda_p)$.

By Lemma E.2 (below), it holds that $\lambda|_{S \setminus \text{out}(\lambda_p)}$ is an admissible labelling of the restriction $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ which uses only active attacks to label assumptions out . Furthermore, $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$. Since $|SCC(D)| > 1$ and any such SCC contains at least one assumption, the restriction $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ must contain strictly less assumptions than D and therefore by the induction hypothesis $\lambda|_{S \setminus \text{out}(\lambda_p)} \in GF_{ad}(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$, so $\lambda' = \lambda|_{S \setminus \text{out}(\lambda_p)}$ is the desired labelling.

(\Leftarrow) Let $\lambda \in GF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$, then $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$. Now suppose to the contrary it does not hold that: λ is admissible and $\text{in}(\lambda)$ attacks all out-labelled assumptions actively.

Then either $\text{in}(\lambda)$ is not a conflict-free set (Case 1), some $a \in \text{in}(\lambda)$ is not defended (Case 2), some $a \in \text{out}(\lambda)$ is not attacked actively by $\text{in}(\lambda)$ (Case 3) or some $a \in \text{und}(\lambda)$ is attacked actively by $\text{in}(\lambda)$ (Case 4).

By the induction hypothesis $\lambda|_{S \setminus \text{out}(\lambda_p)} \in GF_{ad}(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$ is an admissible labelling on $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ for any SCC S .

(Case 1) Then some $a \in \text{in}(\lambda)$ is actively attacked by some $B \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda)$. Let $S \in SCC(D)$ be the SCC

containing a , then by definition of the dependency graph $B \subseteq S \cup PA_D(S)$. Since $\lambda(a) = \text{in}$, we have $\lambda'(a) = \text{in}$ for the admissible labelling λ' of the restriction $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ (induction hypothesis), in particular $a \in \text{in}(\lambda_p)$. So $B \not\subseteq PA_D(S)$, but $B' = B \cap \text{in}(\lambda') \neq \emptyset$ (remember $B \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda)$). Then, since $B \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda_p)$ we have $B \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a^{up}} \bar{a}$, thus the set B' also actively attacks a in $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$. But $B' \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda')$ and $a \in \text{in}(\lambda')$, so that would mean λ' is not admissible. Contradiction.

(Case 2) Then there exists some $B \subseteq (PA_D(S) \cup S), B \cap \text{out}(\lambda) = \emptyset$, which attacks some $a \in \text{in}(\lambda)$, let S again be the SCC containing a . If $B \subseteq PA_D(S)$, then $a \notin \text{in}(\lambda_p)$, because B contains no out-labeled assumptions and therefore a is either defeated or provisionally defeated. But then $a \notin \text{in}(\lambda') \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda_p)$, so either λ does not coincide with λ' on $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ or a is defeated, but not labeled out, both contradict $\lambda \in GF_{ad}(D, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \emptyset)$. So $B \cap S \neq \emptyset$. Furthermore, since $\text{out}(\lambda_p) \subseteq \text{out}(\lambda)$ we have $B \cap \text{out}(\lambda_p) = \emptyset$ and therefore $B \vdash_{\mathcal{R}^{up} \cup \emptyset^{up}} \bar{a}$, so there exists a B' which attacks a actively or at least semi-actively in $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$. But then, since $a \in \text{in}(\lambda')$ and λ' is an admissible labelling of $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ there exists an active attack from $\text{in}(\lambda')$ to some $b \in B'$ in $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$. This implies $\lambda(b) = \lambda'(b) = \text{out}$, so $B \cap \text{out}(\lambda) \neq \emptyset$. Contradiction.

(Case 3) Let S again be the SCC containing a . If $\text{in}(\lambda)$ does not attack a actively, then $a \notin \text{out}(\lambda_p) = \{a \in S \mid (\text{in}(\lambda) \cap PA_D(S)) \text{ actively attacks } a\}$. So $a \in \text{out}(\lambda')$ for a is then contained in $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$. Since λ' is an admissible labelling on $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ which uses only active attacks for its defense, there exists some $B \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda')$ which actively attacks a . But then, by definition of $\mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ and \mathcal{R}_a^{up} , there exists a superset $B' \supseteq B$ such that $B' \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda)$ and B' actively attacks a in D . Contradiction.

(Case 4) Then there exists some $B \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda) \cap (PA_D(S) \cup S)$ which attacks said undecided a actively, let S again be the SCC containing a . If $B \subseteq PA_D(S)$, then $a \in \text{out}(\lambda_p)$ and therefore $a \in \text{out}(\lambda)$, so $B' = B \cap \text{in}(\lambda') \neq \emptyset$. But then B' actively attacks a in $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ (see Case 1), so since $\lambda'(a) = \lambda(a) = \text{und}$ it follows λ' is not an admissible labelling on $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$. Contradiction with the induction hypothesis. \square

One direction of the above proof we capture in the following lemma:

Lemma E.2. *Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ a set of assumptions, $\mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ sets of active and semiactive rules, $\mathcal{R}_a \cup \mathcal{R}_s = \mathcal{R}$, $S \in SCC(D)$ and $\lambda \in \Lambda_{ad}(D)$. The restriction $\lambda|_{S \setminus \text{out}(\lambda_p)}$ is an admissible labelling of the restriction $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ for $\lambda_p(S, \lambda_{PA_D(S)}, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ which uses only*

active attacks to label assumptions out .

Proof. First of all, λ is conflict-free on $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$, for the restricted sets of attacks do not add any conflicts. In particular $B \vdash_R \bar{a}$, where $R = \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p} \cup \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$, for any $B \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda_p) \cup \text{und}(\lambda_p)$, $a \in \text{in}(\lambda|_{S \setminus \text{out}(\lambda_p)})$ iff there is a superset $B' \subseteq (\text{in}(\lambda) \cup \text{und}(\lambda) \cup \text{in}(\lambda_p) \cup \text{und}(\lambda_p))$ attacking a in D , but since λ is an admissible labelling, any such B' contains an out -labeled argument.

Second, $a \in \text{out}(\lambda|_{S \setminus \text{out}(\lambda_p)})$ iff there exists some $B \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda)$ such that $B \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a} \bar{a}$, since λ is an admissible labelling where $\text{in}(\lambda)$ attacks all assumptions labeled out actively wrt. \mathcal{R}_a , thus all attacks by subsets of $\text{in}(\lambda)$ are active wrt. \mathcal{R}_a^{up} , too. It also holds that $\text{in}(\lambda) \cap (\text{out}(\lambda_p) \cup \text{und}(\lambda_p)) = \emptyset$, since any defeated or provisionally defeated arguments cannot be defended by an admissible labelling λ using only active attacks. Therefore $B \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a^{up}} \bar{a}$ and thus $B \cap (\text{in}(\lambda_p) \cup \text{und}(\lambda_p)) \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}} \bar{a}$, so a is actively attacked

by a subset of B in $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$. By the definition of the restriction and the resp. set of active attacks the other direction also holds, i.e., any $B \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda)$ satisfies $B \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}} \bar{a}$ only, if B has a superset $B' \subseteq \text{in}(\lambda)$ which attacks a actively in D .

Third, from the reasoning under the second point it becomes clear, that $\text{in}(\lambda)$ can be defended with active attacks in $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ for any admissible labelling λ . So $\lambda|_{S \setminus \text{out}(\lambda_p)}$ is an admissible labelling of $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$. \square

Corollary E.3. *The admissible semantics for ABA satisfies SCC-recursiveness, i.e., for every ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ and labeling $\lambda: \lambda \in \Lambda_{ad}(D)$ iff $\lambda \in GF_{ad}(D, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \emptyset)$.*

Theorem 5.20. *Each ABA semantics $\sigma \in \{co, pr, st, gr\}$ satisfies SCC-recursiveness.*

Proof. $\sigma = st$ We define $\lambda \in BF_{st}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff

- $\lambda \in BF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$
- $\text{und}(\lambda) = \emptyset$

We now prove the following statement by induction over the size of \mathcal{A} , Base Case $|\mathcal{A}| = 1$.

Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ be an ABAF, $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ a set of assumptions, $\mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ sets of active and semiactive rules, $\mathcal{R}_a \cup \mathcal{R}_s = \mathcal{R}$. Then $\lambda \in GF_{st}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff

- $\lambda \in \Lambda_{st}(D)$ and
- $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and
- for every $a \in \mathcal{A}$ if $\lambda(a) = \text{out}$ then $\text{in}(\lambda) \vdash_{\mathcal{R}_a} \bar{a}$.

For $|\text{SCC}(D)| = 1$, this follows directly from the definition of BF_{st} . This covers the base case.

It is left to show that for $|\text{SCC}(D)| > 1$ it holds that $\lambda \in \Lambda_{st}(D)$ with $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and uses only active attacks for labelling assumptions out iff for every $S \in \text{SCC}(D)$ the partial labelling λ_S coincides on $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ with some

$$\lambda' \in GF_{st}(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$$

and satisfies $\lambda(s) = \text{out}$ for all $s \in S \setminus D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ for $\lambda_p(S, \lambda_{pAD}(S), \mathcal{R}, \emptyset)$ the partial provisional labelling of S .

(\Leftarrow) If $\lambda \in \Lambda_{st}(D)$ (such that $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and using only active attacks for out -labels), then $\lambda \in \Lambda_{ad}(D)$ (such that $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and using only active attacks for out -labels), so we have $\lambda|_{D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}} \in GF_{ad}(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$ for any SCC S by Lemma E.2 and the induction hypothesis. Furthermore $\lambda|_{D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}}$ is a partial labelling of λ , so $\text{und}(\lambda|_{D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}}) = \emptyset$. Thus $\lambda|_{D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}} \in GF_{ad}(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$, so a suitable λ' exists for any S .

(\Rightarrow) By the induction hypothesis $GF_{st}(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}) \subseteq GF_{ad}(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$ for any SCC S , so $\lambda \in \Lambda_{ad}(D)$ (such that $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and using only active attacks for out -labels). Furthermore, since for any S the labelling λ' on the restriction $D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}$ only assigns the labels in and out , and since the defeated assumptions $a \in \text{out}(\lambda_p)$ are labeled out , $\text{und}(\lambda) = \emptyset$. So $\lambda \in \Lambda_{st}(D)$ (such that $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$ and using only active attacks for out -labels).

For $\sigma \in \{co, pr, gr\}$, we define the respective base functions. From there, one can reason analogously to the case $\sigma = st$ via a proof by induction.

$\sigma = co$ We define $\lambda \in BF_{co}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff

- $\lambda \in BF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$
- for every $a \in E$ it holds that if $\text{in}(\lambda)$ defends a then $a \in \text{in}(\lambda)$.

$\sigma = pr$ We define $\lambda \in BF_{pr}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff

- $\lambda \in BF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$
- there is no $\lambda' \in BF_{ad}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ such that $\text{in}(\lambda')$ is a proper superset of $\text{in}(\lambda)$.

$\sigma = gr$ We define $\lambda \in BF_{gr}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ iff

- $\lambda \in BF_{co}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$
- there is no $\lambda' \in BF_{co}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$ such that $\text{in}(\lambda')$ is a proper subset of $\text{in}(\lambda)$. \square

F Omitted Proofs of Subsection 5.3

Lemma F.1. *Let σ be SCC-recursive, admissible and universal. Then $GF_{\sigma}(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s) \neq \emptyset$ for any ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ with $|\text{SCC}(D)| = 1$, set of assumptions $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and set of active and semi-active attacks $\mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s \subseteq \mathcal{R}$.*

Proof. Consider the ABAF $D' = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}', \neg)$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}' &= \mathcal{A} \cup \{a_r \mid r \in \mathcal{R}_s\} \\ \mathcal{R}' &= \mathcal{R}_a \cup \{\text{head}(r) \leftarrow \text{body}(r) \cup \{a_r\} \mid r \in \mathcal{R}_s\} \\ &\quad \cup \{\bar{a} \leftarrow \{a\} \mid a \notin E\} \cup \{\bar{a}_r \leftarrow \{a_r\} \mid r \in \mathcal{R}_s\} \end{aligned}$$

with $\bar{a}' = \bar{a}$ for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$ (we just add arbitrary contraries for the additional assumptions a_r).

Since σ is universal, it holds that $\Lambda_{\sigma}(D') \neq \emptyset$. Since σ is SCC-recursive, it follows that there exists some σ -labelling $\lambda \in GF_{\sigma}(D', \mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}', \emptyset)$. Since $\text{in}(\lambda)$ is admissible (because

σ is admissible) it follows that $\text{in}(\lambda) \subseteq E$. Furthermore, \mathcal{A} is an SCC of D' with $\{\{a_r\} | r \in \mathcal{R}_s \text{ as its set of parent SCCs. Since } \sigma \text{ is SCC-recursive, there must exist some } \lambda' \in GF_\sigma(D' \downarrow_{\mathcal{A}}^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_{\mathcal{A}}^{\lambda_p}, \mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_{\mathcal{A}}^{\lambda_p})$. Because $a_r \notin \text{in}(\lambda)$ there are no defeated assumptions and the restriction contains all $a \in \mathcal{A}$, so $D' \downarrow_{\mathcal{A}}^{\lambda_p} = D$. Furthermore the active rules of the restriction are exactly those without participation of some a_r , which are the rules in \mathcal{R}_a , so $\mathcal{R}_a \downarrow_{\mathcal{A}}^{\lambda_p} = \mathcal{R}_a$ and $\mathcal{R}_s \downarrow_{\mathcal{A}}^{\lambda_p} = \mathcal{R}_s$, since the a_r are all undecided under λ , because λ is an admissible labelling. Since λ' coincides with λ on D it holds that $\text{in}(\lambda') \subseteq E$. So $\lambda' \in GF_\sigma(D, E, \mathcal{R}_a, \mathcal{R}_s)$. \square

We recall the definitions for universal and admissible semantics.

Definition F.2. We say a semantics σ is

universal iff $\Lambda_\sigma(D) \neq \emptyset$ for every ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, -)$

admissible iff $\text{in}(\lambda)$ is an admissible set for all $\lambda \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$.

Theorem 5.24. If σ is SCC-recursive, admissible, and universal, then I_σ satisfies the SCC-Markov condition.

Proof. Let $S \in SCC(D)$ for some ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, -)$. We have to show that for any σ -labellings λ_1, λ_2 which agree on the parents $PA_D(S)$, i.e., $\lambda_1|_{PA_D(S)} = \lambda_2|_{PA_D(S)}$, we can find a σ -labelling λ_3 , such that $\lambda_3|_{ND_D(S) \cup PA_D(S)} = \lambda_1|_{ND_D(S) \cup PA_D(S)}$ and $\lambda_3|_S = \lambda_2|_S$.

To do so, we choose a partial labelling $\lambda_3|_T$ on every SCC $T \in SCC(D)$ as follows:

For $T \in ND_D(S) \cup PA_D(S)$ $\lambda_3|_T = \lambda_1|_T$,

for $T = S$ $\lambda_3|_T = \lambda_2|_T$,

for $T \in SCC(D) \setminus (ND_D(S) \cup PA_D(S) \cup \{S\})$ if $\lambda_3|_{PA_D(T)}$ is already set, we

1. determine $\lambda_p(T, \lambda_3|_{PA_D(T)}, \mathcal{R}, \emptyset)$
2. set $\lambda_3|_{\text{out}(\lambda_p)}(a) = \text{out}$ for all $a \in \text{out}(\lambda_p)$
3. choose $\lambda_3|_{D \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p}} = \lambda'$ to be some

$$\lambda' \in GF_\sigma(D \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R} \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p}, \emptyset \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p})$$

otherwise we recursively choose $\lambda_3|_{PA_D(T)}$ first by choosing a partial labelling for each parent SCC of T .

The choice of λ_3 is well-defined (but non-deterministic), since the SCC-graph is acyclic. Furthermore, since σ is universal, SCC-recursive and admissible, the set $GF_\sigma(D \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R} \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p}, \emptyset \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p})$ of σ -labellings on the restriction of T is not empty for any chosen partial labelling $\lambda_3|_{PA_D(T)}$ on the parents by Lemma F.1.

It is left to show, that we CAN indeed choose the restriction of λ_1 for $T \in ND_D(S) \cup PA_D(S)$ and λ_2 for $T = S$ without violating the recursive composition of λ_3 . Since σ is SCC-recursive and $\lambda_2, \lambda_1 \in \Lambda_\sigma(D)$, it holds that

- for all $T \in ND_D(S) \cup PA_D(S)$ we have $\lambda_3|_{D \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p}} = \lambda_1|_{D \downarrow_T^{\lambda_p}} \in GF_\sigma(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R} \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \emptyset \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$ and $\lambda_3|_{\text{out}(\lambda_p)}(a) = \text{out}$ for all $a \in \text{out}(\lambda_p)$ for $\lambda_p(T, \lambda_3|_{PA_D(T)}, \mathcal{R}, \emptyset)$, since $\lambda_3|_{PA_D(T)} = \lambda_1|_{PA_D(T)}$,

- for S we have $\lambda_3|_{D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}} = \lambda_2|_{D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}} \in GF_\sigma(D \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \text{in}(\lambda_p), \mathcal{R} \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p}, \emptyset \downarrow_S^{\lambda_p})$ and $\lambda_3|_{\text{out}(\lambda_p)}(a) = \text{out}$ for all $a \in \text{out}(\lambda_p)$ for $\lambda_p(S, \lambda_3|_{PA_D(S)}, \mathcal{R}, \emptyset)$ since $\lambda_3|_{PA_D(S)} = \lambda_1|_{PA_D(S)} = \lambda_2|_{PA_D(S)}$

Therefore, since σ is SCC-recursive, λ_3 is a σ -labelling. \square

Note that the other direction does not hold, i.e., not every Universal, admissible semantics σ for which I_σ satisfies the SCC-Markov condition is SCC-recursive. For example, let $\sigma(D) = pr(D)$ for every ABAF D with $|SCC(D)| = 1$, but $\sigma(D') = \{\emptyset\}$ for all other ABAFs D' . Then I_σ satisfies the SCC-Markov condition, because there is only a single extension for any relevant ABAF, but σ is not SCC-recursive. For further discussion see [Rienstra et al., 2020].

Theorem 5.26. Let $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, -)$ be an ABAF and σ be SCC-Markovian. Then, for disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ of assumptions, $A \perp_a B \mid C$ in G_D implies $A \perp_\sigma B \mid C$ in D .

Proof. We make use of the result by Verma and Pearl (1988) (cf. Theorem A.6): if an independence model I is a semi-graphoid over a set of variables X that satisfies the local Markov condition with respect to a DAG G , then d-separation in G implies independence wrt. I .

Let D be the given ABAF, P_D the dependency graph and $G_D = (V, E)$ the d-graph of D . Let S_1, \dots, S_n denote the SCCs of P_D and let s_1, \dots, s_n denote the nodes corresponding to the SCCs in G_D . To make use of the theorem by Pearl and Verma, we extend the valuation of P_D to G_D so that we obtain an independence model I over \mathcal{A} which is a semi-graphoid and satisfies the local Markov condition with respect to G_D . The proof uses similar ideas like the proof of [Rienstra et al., 2020, Theorem 3] in the setting of abstract argumentation.

Given a σ -labelling λ of \mathcal{A} , we define the corresponding generalized labelling of G_D (cf. Definition A.5) by assigning each node s_i a tuple corresponding to the labels of its members. Formally, we define the generalisation as follows:

$$\lambda^*(x) = \begin{cases} \lambda(x) & \text{if } x \in \mathcal{A} \\ (\lambda(a_1), \dots, \lambda(a_m)) & \text{if } x = s_i, \\ & \text{for } S_i \in SCC(P_D), \\ & S_i = \{a_1, \dots, a_m\} \end{cases}$$

Now, we show that this is a faithful generalisation of our independence notion I . We show that (i) I is a semi-graphoid over \mathcal{A} and (ii) I satisfies the local Markov condition with respect to G_D .

- (i) By definition, $\{\lambda^*|_{\mathcal{A}} \mid \lambda \in \sigma(D)\} = \sigma(D)$; hence, by Proposition 4.5, σ -independence in G_D satisfies the semi-graphoid axioms.
- (ii) We show that $\{x\} \perp_I ND_{G_D}(\{x\}) \mid Pa_{G_D}(\{x\})$ for every $x \in N$. Note that by definition of G_D , either (a) x is an SCC-node or (b) $Pa_{G_D}(\{x\})$ is an SCC-node. We proceed with case distinction.

- **Case a:** Let $x = s_i$ be an SCC-node and consider arbitrary labellings λ_1^*, λ_2^* of $\{x\} \cup Pa_{G_D}(\{x\})$

and $ND_{G_D}(\{x\}) \cup Pa_{G_D}(\{x\})$, respectively. We utilise the SCC-Markovian property in the corresponding dependency graph P_D as follows: (1) from $ND_{G_D}(\{x\})$, remove all parent SCC nodes s_j of s_i ; (2) replace each SCC-node s in the sets $\{x\}$, $ND_{G_D}(\{x\})$ and $Pa_{G_D}(\{x\})$ with the assumptions contained in s . The resulting sets are s_i , $ND_{P_D}(s_i)$ and $Pa_{P_D}(s_i)$, respectively. By assumption, σ is SCC-Markovian and it holds that $s_i \perp_I ND_{P_D}(s_i) \mid Pa_{P_D}(s_i)$. We therefore obtain a labelling λ_3^* which realises $\{x\} \cup ND_{G_D}(\{x\}) \cup Pa_{G_D}(\{x\})$ (for this, we project our initial labellings to \mathcal{A} and extend the labelling which witnesses independence between the sets accordingly).

- **Case b:** Let $s = Pa_{G_D}(\{x\})$ be an SCC-node. By construction, it holds that $x \in s$. Consider arbitrary labellings λ_1^*, λ_2^* of $\{x\} \cup s$ and $ND_{G_D}(\{x\}) \cup s$, respectively. By definition of λ^* , the labelling of s determines the labellings of the assumptions contained in s . Thus, the labelling λ_2^* already serves as a witness of independence of $\{x\}$ and $ND_{G_D}(\{x\})$, given $Pa_{G_D}(\{x\})$ (set $\lambda_3^* := \lambda_2^*$).

We obtain that for all disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ of assumptions, if A and B are d-separated in G_D , given C , then A and B are σ -independent, given C . \square

We conclude by showing that the method is indeed polynomial in the size of the given ABAF D .

Proposition F.3. *Checking independence using the d-graph method for ABA is in P.*

Proof. Constructing the dependency graph P_D for a given ABAF $D = (\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{A}, \neg)$ can be done in linear time (traverse the rule set). The d-graph of any graph can be constructed in P [Rienstra *et al.*, 2020], and the independence check via d-separation is in P, cf. Lemma A.7. \square